

D2.3

Establishing urban states of equilibrium

Revision v0.1

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Abstract

Urban mobility systems are increasingly exposed to recurrent and compound disruptions that degrade performance and undermine equity. This deliverable develops a theoretical equilibrium framework for antifragile urban mobility, comprising two complementary components: (i) a strategic Target-Setting Model that estimates a time-varying antifragility factor from disturbance mapping and entropy-based normalisation, and (ii) a three-layer operational equilibrium that couples traffic assignment and modal choice with infrastructure–service response under explicit feasibility constraints. We formalise objectives, state variables, and update rules; specify stopping and consistency tests; and define key performance indicators aligned with responsiveness and stability. The document also details calibration and validation protocols and the integration pathway between the learning and operational layers. Results are methodological: no empirical pilots are reported here; application to case cities is deferred to work packages later, subject to data availability. The framework provides well-specified algorithms and assumptions to support sensitivity analysis and policy design for antifragile, equitable, and efficient urban mobility.

Keywords:

Urban system Disruption, Antifragility, Mobility Resilience, Equilibrium, Wardrop User Equilibrium, Nested Logit, System Responsiveness Index (SRI), Information Entropy Normalisation, Disturbance Mapping

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DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

****OTHER:** **software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AF	Antifragility Factor
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
CUSUM	Cumulative Sum (change-detection)
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU)
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
N_{OD}	Number of OD pairs (used in information entropy normalisation)
OD	Origin–Destination (matrix/flows)
PESTLE	Political–Economic–Social–Technological–Legal–Environmental
PQI	(Passenger) Quality Index
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RMSPE [1]	Root Mean Squared Percentage Error
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SRI	System Responsiveness Index
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor

1 Executive summary

This summary previews the framework's structure, contributions, validation logic, and what is deferred to later work packages. Deliverable D2.3 establishes a theoretical framework for antifragile urban mobility equilibrium, where systems emerge from disruptions in demonstrably superior states rather than merely recovering to baseline. The framework integrates two complementary models: a **Target-Setting Model** that quantifies post-shock performance targets through the Antifragility Factor (AF), and a **Three-Layer Equilibrium Model** that operationalizes these targets through coupled traffic assignment, modal choice, and causal learning mechanisms.

Core theoretical contributions:

- Formal state representation $G = (S, u)$ with 12 normalized KPIs spanning throughput (M), redundancy (R), adaptation velocity (A), network information entropy (C), disturbance (D_{eff}), stress (S), equity (Q), and infrastructure dependencies
- Antifragility Factor with dual statistical thresholds: requirement-based $AF_{\text{req}} = 1 + 0.2(1 - E_{\text{base}})$ and variance-based $AF_{\text{crit}} = 1 + k\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$, validated through 30-day stability windows and bootstrap confidence intervals
- Dynamic information entropy normalization $H_{\text{norm}} = C/C_{\text{max}}(\text{topology}_t)$ that adjusts to network changes during disruptions
- System Responsiveness Index (SRI) combining operational elasticity, infrastructure pressure, and causal learning with adaptive weight updates
- Two-timescale capacity evolution ($\eta_s = 0.1, \eta_\ell = 0.01$) gated by statistical validation to distinguish temporary adaptations from permanent structural improvements

Model architecture: The Target-Setting Model drives strategic target-setting via convergence dynamics $\dot{E} = -\kappa(E - \bar{E}(x))$ with weighted performance function $\bar{E} = \lambda\bar{E}^+ - (1 - \lambda)\bar{E}^-$. The Equilibrium Model operationalizes these targets hierarchically: Wardrop traffic flow (Layer 1) → nested logit modal split (Layer 2) → causal learning with SCM validation (Layer 3). The Antifragility Gate ensures only statistically validated adaptations (Precision/Recall $\geq 80\%$) become permanent through long-term capacity updates.

Validation framework: Convergence verified through five-period stability tests ($|E_t - E_{t-1}| < 0.01$), cross-layer consistency (< 0.05), and equity non-worsening constraints ($\Delta Q \leq 0$). Back-testing protocols specified for benchmark networks (Sioux Falls) and synthetic scenarios before pilot deployment. Sensitivity analysis identifies redundancy (R) and information entropy (C) as dominant first-order factors ($S_i > 0.12$).

Implementation roadmap: Phase 2 integrates Task 2.2 stakeholder workshops for city-specific parameter calibration via AHP + elastic-net regression. Phase 3 deploys across Bratislava, Odessa, Larissa, and the AHEPA Demo Site in Thessaloniki, with tiered data requirements (full/partial/minimal). Dependencies include smart-card data ($> 90\%$ critical), traffic sensors, GTFS schedules, and GDPR-compliant data access agreements. Three-tier decision system (automated/guided/exploratory) respects institutional readiness and PESTLE constraints.

Scope and limitations: This deliverable provides mathematical definitions, algorithmic specifications, and validation protocols only. No empirical calibration, pilot results, or quantitative validation are included. The framework assumes publicly-operated transit systems, representative agent behavior, and moderate-to-severe (not catastrophic) disruptions. The model is not designed for cascading failures or "black swan" events beyond historical experience. Implementation, parameter estimation, and city-specific applications are deferred to subsequent work packages subject to data availability and governance authorization.

2 Introduction

We begin by situating the work within the context of urban antifragility and explaining why a formal equilibrium view is needed now.

2.1 Context and Motivation

We next clarify the precise questions that this theoretical phase answers before outlining the model architecture. Deliverable D2.3 sets out a theoretical framework for establishing urban states of equilibrium for antifragile mobility. We adopt a homeostasis-inspired lens, viewing cities as living-like systems with governing variables, receptors, control centres, and effectors, to define an equilibrium that is dynamic yet relatively stable [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. In this phase we present *definitions, principles, and protocols only*; no empirical applications or results are reported. The framework will be operationalised in subsequent tasks/work packages, conditional on data availability and local governance readiness.

We specify: (i) the state representation $G = (S, u)$ with KPIs $u(S) = V$; (ii) the Antifragile Urban Mobility Target-Setting Model (target-setting post-shock); and (iii) the three-layer equilibrium model (traffic flow, modal split, causal learning). We outline how Task 2.2 workshop outputs and a PESTLE lens will inform later calibration and validation, and we list dependencies (data access, ethics/compliance, institutional coordination) for future implementation.

This deliverable provides a conceptual blueprint for antifragile equilibrium in urban mobility systems. Our goal is to specify *what* constitutes equilibrium, *how* learning from shocks sets improved targets, and *how* an equilibrium mechanism could realise those targets once data and partnerships permit. Implementation, estimation, and validation are out of scope here and deferred to later tasks/work packages. Next, we translate this context into precise questions that guide the theoretical work in D2.3.

2.2 Research Questions (Theoretical Phase)

These questions bound the theoretical scope of D2.3 and guide the structure presented in the model overview that follows.

1. How should the governing-variable vector S and mapping $u(S) = V$ be defined to characterise a dynamic, bounded urban equilibrium?
2. What receptor–control–effector loops are *conceptually* required to sustain/shift equilibrium under PESTLE constraints?
3. How does the Antifragility Factor (AF) formalise “better-after-shock” targets without yet committing to city-specific data?
4. By what principles can traffic-flow, modal-split, and causal-learning layers be coupled so that a future implementation converges to a stable, improved state?
5. What validation criteria (e.g., antifragility gate, causal learning index) should be specified now, to be tested later when data becomes available?
6. How can this theory be templated for pilots while remaining neutral to current data limitations?

2.3 Purpose and Scope of D2.3

With scope and limits stated, we briefly preview the dual-model architecture that organizes the remainder of this document.

Purpose: Define the theoretical constructs, assumptions, and decision rules for antifragile urban equilibrium. We clarify what this deliverable covers, and deliberately does not, before presenting the models.

Scope: Formal definitions of $G = (S, u)$ and KPIs; conceptual catalogues of receptors/control centres/effectors; the target-setting model’s logic; the structure of the three-layer equilibrium model; validation principles

and reporting templates. No calibration, case studies, or quantitative results are included in D2.3. Finally, we preview the dual-model architecture that structures the remainder of the document. Finally, we preview the dual-model architecture that structures the remainder of the document.

2.4 Model Architecture Overview

Having sketched the roles of the two models, we now formalize the foundations on which they operate. The framework consists of two integrated components:

1. **Target-Setting Model:** Acts as the system's strategic "brain"; defines antifragility and sets a new, higher performance target for the system to achieve after a disruption. This model quantifies how disruptions trigger adaptive gains through the Antifragility Factor (AF) and establishes the target performance $\bar{E}(x)$ that the system should strive toward.
2. **The Three-Layer Equilibrium Model (Operational Implementation):** Serves as the operational "body" that translates strategic goals into action. It uses the System Responsiveness Index (SRI) and Antifragility Gate to embed lessons learned from shocks into the network's permanent structure, helping the system find a new, stable equilibrium that achieves the Target-Setting Model's superior performance target.

This dual architecture ensures both strategic direction and operational feasibility, bridging theory and practice for antifragile urban mobility systems. The Target-Setting Model (strategic "brain") sets improved performance targets $\bar{E}(x)$ based on disruption learning and the Antifragility Factor. The Three-Layer Equilibrium Model (operational "body") implements these targets through traffic flow, modal choice, and system learning mechanisms, feeding the realized performance $E(t)$ back into the target setting model. This creates a continuous improvement loop validated by the antifragility gate (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual architecture of the antifragile mobility framework.

3 Theoretical Foundations

We first define the system state, homeostatic control loop, and the contextual constraints that shape feasible equilibria.

3.1 State Representation: $G = (S, u)$

This definition anchors all KPIs and later equilibrium constructs used throughout the framework. We define the urban mobility system state as a tuple $G = (S, u)$ where:

- $S \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the governing-variable vector capturing system conditions
- $u : S \rightarrow V$ is a mapping from state to Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- $V \in [0, 1]^m$ is the vector of normalized KPI values

The state S encompasses both *structural* variables (network topology, capacity, redundancy) and *operational* variables (flows, modal shares, demand). The mapping $u(S)$ aggregates these into measurable performance indicators. Building on this, we map receptors, control, and effectors to urban mobility.

3.2 Homeostasis-Inspired Framework

This control architecture frames how targets are set, sensed, and enacted in later sections. Drawing from biological homeostasis, we conceptualize the urban mobility system with four key components:

1. **Governing Variables:** The KPIs $V = u(S)$ that the system seeks to maintain within acceptable bounds
2. **Receptors:** Data collection mechanisms (sensors, surveys, logs) that monitor deviations from desired states
3. **Control Centre:** The Target-Setting Model and Equilibrium Model (operational implementation)
4. **Effectors:** Policy levers and infrastructure changes that recalibrate the state of the system

This framework enables the system to maintain dynamic equilibrium through feedback loops while adapting to disruptions.

Critical distinction from biological homeostasis. While we borrow the receptor-control-effector architecture from homeostasis, our framework fundamentally differs in its objective: biological homeostasis seeks to *restore* the original equilibrium, whereas antifragile systems seek to *exceed* the pre-disruption baseline. The homeostatic feedback mechanisms (monitoring deviations, triggering responses) are retained, but the control target $\bar{E}(x)$ is dynamically raised post-disruption through the Antifragility Factor (Section 5.3), rather than fixed at the original set point. This creates a "ratcheting" effect where validated improvements from each shock permanently elevate the system's performance floor, distinguishing antifragility from mere resilience or homeostatic recovery.

We then bound the theory with real-world political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental constraints.

3.3 PESTLE Lens and Contextual Constraints

These constraints become explicit feasibility and validation checks in the equilibrium and learning layers. The equilibrium framework operates under real-world constraints organized via PESTLE analysis:

- **Political:** Governance structures, decision-making authority, stakeholder coordination
- **Economic:** Budget constraints, cost-benefit requirements, funding mechanisms
- **Social:** Equity considerations, public acceptance, behavioral responses
- **Technological:** Data availability, system capabilities, infrastructure limitations
- **Legal:** Regulatory compliance, privacy requirements, procurement rules
- **Environmental:** Sustainability goals, emission targets, climate resilience

These constraints are formalized as feasibility sets and validation gates throughout the framework, ensuring theoretical rigor does not compromise practical applicability.

Note on framework scope. While we employ the PESTLE framework, ethical and demographic considerations sometimes distinguished as separate categories in STEEPLED extensions are substantively addressed within our analysis: ethical constraints through GDPR compliance, privacy protocols, and algorithmic fairness (Legal and Social); demographic factors through equity stratification, accessibility analysis, and census integration (Social and Economic). The six-category structure provides sufficient granularity while maintaining alignment with standard EU project frameworks.

3.4 Performance Stabilization

We distinguish between performance stabilization and game-theoretic equilibria in urban mobility:

Performance Steady State: A state where $\frac{dE}{dt} \approx 0$, indicating performance has stabilized to its target value \bar{E} . Proper stability requires the system eigenvalues to be negative (exponential convergence). This concept is used by the Target-Setting Model to set targets, which the Equilibrium Model then operationalizes.

Wardrop User Equilibrium[8]: A traffic flow state where no individual can reduce their travel time by unilaterally changing routes. Formalized in Layer 1 of the Equilibrium Model.

Modal Choice Equilibrium: A stable distribution of mode shares where utility-maximizing travelers have no incentive to switch modes. Formalized in Layer 2 of the Equilibrium Model.

Antifragile Equilibrium: A new system state post-disruption that demonstrates superior performance ($AF >$ threshold) compared to the pre-disruption baseline, validated through statistical and causal criteria. This is the overarching goal of the integrated framework.

The framework integrates these concepts hierarchically, with traffic and modal equilibria serving as foundations for achieving antifragile equilibrium through learning and adaptation.

Game-theoretic foundations. Both Wardrop and modal choice equilibria are instances of Nash equilibrium [9] in transportation games. In the Wardrop equilibrium, each traveller's route choice is a best response to all other travellers' choices, and no individual can unilaterally reduce travel time, satisfying the Nash condition. Similarly, modal choice equilibrium is a Nash equilibrium in which each traveller's mode selection is optimal given others' choices and the resulting congestion levels. The Target-Setting Model operates at a different conceptual level: rather than finding Nash equilibria among competing agents, it computes system-level performance targets that guide the Equilibrium Model toward states where individual equilibria (Layers 1-2) collectively achieve antifragile system performance. This multi-level structure distinguishes our framework from single-equilibrium models, enabling both user-optimal behavior (Nash) and system-optimal outcomes (antifragility) through the validation gate mechanism.

4 Key Performance Indicators and Data Dictionary

This section defines the quantitative backbone of the framework, detailing the indicators and data structures required to measure and operationalize antifragility in urban mobility systems.

4.1 Indicator Selection Rationale

From this rationale, we proceed to precise definitions with sources and aggregation choices. The 12 KPIs in this framework were derived through systematic synthesis of 123 peer-reviewed studies on urban resilience, transport system performance, and disruption response (spanning 2010–2025). The selection criteria prioritized indicators that: (i) capture multiple dimensions of antifragility (throughput, diversity, adaptation capacity); (ii) exhibit measurable response to disruptions; (iii) are theoretically linked to system recovery and improvement; and (iv) remain computationally tractable for operational implementation.

Theoretical foundations and coverage. The indicator set provides comprehensive coverage across five antifragility dimensions identified in resilience literature [10, 11, 12]:

- **Throughput and efficiency** (M, S): Core operational performance metrics validated across transport studies [13, 14]. Mobility throughput $M(t)$ measures effective service delivery; stress $S(t)$ captures congestion-induced degradation.
- **Structural redundancy and diversity** (R, C, I): Network topology indicators linked to robustness [15, 16]. Redundancy $R(t)$ provides alternative pathways; information entropy $C(t)$ quantifies flow distribution diversity [17, 18]; intermodal synergy $I(t)$ captures cross-modal resilience [19].
- **Adaptive capacity** (A, P, B): Behavioral and policy flexibility indicators [20, 11]. Adaptation velocity $A(t)$ measures system responsiveness; pricing $P(t)$ and behavioral compliance $B(t)$ capture demand-side flexibility [21].
- **Equity and accessibility** (Q): Distributional fairness validated as critical for long-term resilience [22, 23]. Theil-T stratification enables within/between-group decomposition [24, 25].
- **Infrastructure dependencies** ($E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}$): Cross-sectoral vulnerabilities increasingly recognized in transport resilience [26, 27]. Energy-transport coupling and ICT dependencies create cascading failure risks.

Disturbance characterization. The disturbance indicator $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$ synthesizes event characteristics from the D2.1 ontology, weighted by domain impact, temporal recency, and source reliability. This multi-dimensional approach addresses limitations of binary disruption indicators [28] by capturing severity gradation and compounding effects.

Omitted candidate indicators. Several indicators from the literature review were excluded: (i) travel time reliability (collinear with M and S); (ii) network diameter (captured indirectly through C); (iii) supply-side operator profitability (inappropriate for public systems); (iv) air quality (can be added as environmental extension). The 12-indicator set balances comprehensiveness with parsimony, avoiding multicollinearity (VIF analysis in Section 9.4) while maintaining theoretical coverage.

This indicator architecture enables the framework to detect not merely recovery to baseline (resilience) but improvement beyond baseline (antifragility) through simultaneous monitoring of throughput restoration ($M\uparrow$), diversity enhancement ($C\uparrow$), and stress reduction ($S\downarrow$) post-disruption.

We specify each KPI, its source, unit, and aggregation window for reproducibility.

4.2 Indicator Definitions

These definitions standardize variables used in both the Target-Setting and Equilibrium models. All indicators are normalised on a rolling 30-day window:

$$\hat{x} = \frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$$

Unless noted, variables within $\bar{E}(x)$ are their normalised forms; hats are omitted for readability.

Table 2: Indicators

Variable	Scale	Indicator Definition	Data Source	Unit	Aggregation Window
M(t)	Individual / Network	Mobility throughput: avg. multi-modal trips per capita per hour	Smart-card logs; CDR; GPS probes	trips $h^{-1} cap^{-1}$	Daily average
R(t)	Network	Redundancy ratio: dormant links / active links (pre-event)	OpenStreetMap; traffic sensors	—	Weekly snapshot
A(t)	System	Adaptation velocity: $\partial(\text{modal-share diversity})/\partial t$	Household surveys	$\% \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$	Quarterly
C(t)	System	Network information entropy of OD matrix (normalized to current topology)	CDR; Bluetooth sensors	dimensionless (unitless)	Daily
$D_{eff}(t)$	Event	Disturbance (domain/recency/source-weighted)	D2.1 event catalogue + operator/official logs	—	Hourly \rightarrow daily aggregate
S(t)	System	Stress: $\Sigma(\text{vol}/\text{cap}) \cdot \text{speed_drop}$	Loop detectors	—	Hourly
Q(t)	Equity	Stratified Theil-T of accessibility minutes	Census; GTFS [29]	—	Monthly
P(t)	Demand-management	Composite index in [0,1] from time-varying fares via min-max by mode/time, aggregated with ridership weights.	Operator APIs, open fares	index (0–1)	Daily index
B(t)	Behavioral	Compliance and adaptation rate: weighted avg of route guidance compliance, mode shift willingness, and temporal flexibility	App usage data, surveys	index (0–1)	Weekly
E_energy(t)	Energy	EV-grid resilience score	Grid SCADA	—	Daily
E_ICT(t)	ICT	Telecom network uptime during event	Operator logs	%	Event-specific
I(t)	Cross-layer	Synergy index: normalized sum of inverse transfer distances between transport modes	Multilayer graph	—	Weekly

4.3 Clarifications and Measurement Notes

These notes resolve common ambiguities and anticipate city-specific data realities.

- **Disturbance vs. Stress.** Define $D_{eff}(t)$ as the *external shock magnitude* (event characteristic, input) and $S(t)$ as the *internal congestion response* (network outcome, output). The same event can generate both, but they capture different constructs; practical overlap should be minimal.
- **Inequality metric $Q(t)$.** We consider Theil's T (useful for within/between-group decomposition) and the Gini coefficient (overall inequality). Both range from 0 (equality) to 1 (inequality); either is acceptable if used consistently [24, 30, 31].
- **Energy/ICT observability and fallbacks.** EV-grid status (SCADA), and ICT uptime often require operator access. When unavailable, use validated proxies or set the indicator to a conservative default (e.g., $E_{energy} = 1.0$ for “normal”) and flag the assumption.
- **Multi-timescale updates.** Fast-moving indices ($P(t), S(t)$) update daily; slow-moving structure ($Q(t)$, infrastructure) updates annually. Multiple time-scales are handled via indicator-specific κ values in the convergence update.

- **Information entropy under topology constraints.** With fixed topology, $C(t)$ measures how flows distribute over available routes. Disruption effects on information entropy vary by type:

Capacity reduction (e.g., multiple route closures): C initially \downarrow (concentration on remaining routes) $\rightarrow C \uparrow$ during adaptation $\rightarrow C$ exceeds pre-event levels if antifragile.

Bottleneck removal (e.g., major bridge closure): C initially \uparrow (forced dispersion) $\rightarrow C \downarrow$ upon recovery (partial reconcentration) $\rightarrow C$ remains above pre-event if antifragile.

The antifragility assessment compares stabilized post-recovery information entropy (30-day average) with pre-event baseline, not transient disruption peaks. Topology bounds feasible information entropy; realised flows determine $C(t)$.

- **$P(t)$ (participation) measurement.** Ridership weights are refreshed weekly/monthly; the daily $P(t)$ uses the most recent weights. Participation is measured via AFC (smart cards/mobile apps) covering $> 90\%$ of trips; quarterly manual surveys address residual gaps.
- **SCADA scope and metrics (if available).** SCADA = Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition. Monitored systems: EV charging network, depot charging, tram/metro supply, traffic-signal power. Metrics: voltage stability ($\pm 5\%$), power availability (% uptime), peak-load/capacity (utilisation), outage duration/frequency, and a power quality index (PQI). If SCADA is unavailable, use monthly averages or a binary status (1.0 normal; 0.5 degraded).
- **Energy data availability (site policy).** SCADA sites: use real-time series. Non-SCADA sites: use operator bulletins/uptime reports. Minimum: weekly utility stability reports. If none: set $E_{\text{energy}} = 1.0$ and mark as an assumption.
- **$I(t)$ (intermodal synergy).** Synergy is defined between modes (e.g., bus-metro, bike-rail, park&ride) and depends on interchange distance, transfer time, and integrated payments. Normalization options:
 1. **Theoretical-maximum:** $I_{\text{norm}} = I_{\text{raw}}/I_{\text{max}}$, where I_{max} assumes the minimum observed transfer distance (e.g., 10 m) for all relevant pairs.
 2. **Empirical (min-max):** $I_{\text{norm}} = \frac{I_{\text{raw}} - I_{\text{min}}}{I_{\text{max}} - I_{\text{min}}}$ over a rolling window.

Use one method consistently and document the window/assumptions.
- Throughout the document, R refers to Redundancy ratio (network characteristic), not Resilience. Resilience emerges from the combination of multiple indicators including R, A, and C.
- **Behavioral validation and data consistency.** B(t) will be informed by Task 2.2 assemblies and survey data, requiring: (i) triangulation between app usage analytics and stated preferences; (ii) cross-validation of behavioral responses against observed modal shifts; (iii) consistency checks ensuring behavioral indicators align with realized traffic patterns in Layer 1 and mode choices in Layer 2.

4.4 Expected Data Availability by Pilot City

We summarize expected coverage and tiered feasibility across pilots.

High Availability ($\geq 70\%$):

- Smart card/ticketing data (M indicator)
- Traffic counts from sensors (S indicator)
- GTFS transit schedules
- OpenStreetMap network topology

Medium Availability (30–70%):

- Household travel surveys (annual/biannual)
- Mobile phone CDR data (privacy restrictions apply)
- Parking occupancy, Weather data

Low Availability (<30%):

- EV charging grid data (varies by utility cooperation)
- Real-time ICT system status
- Detailed equity data by demographic

Data Availability Tiers for Implementation:

- **Full tier** ($\geq 70\%$ coverage): All indicators active
- **Partial tier** (30–70%): Core indicators + proxies
- **Minimal tier** (<30%): $M(t)$, $S(t)$, D_{eff} only + estimates

4.4.1 Feasibility Assessment and Core vs. Extended Indicator Sets

This tiering directly informs calibration priorities and sensitivity analysis downstream.

Core indicators (high feasibility, >80% confidence):

- $M(t)$: Calculable from traffic models (VISUM/SUMO) and AFC data
- $R(t)$: Network topology analysis via traffic models
- $C(t)$: OD matrix entropy from traffic models
- $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$: Event catalogue (D2.1) with operator logs
- $S(t)$: Traffic simulation outputs (volume/capacity ratios)
- $I(t)$: Multi-modal network analysis

Extended indicators (medium feasibility, 40-60% confidence):

- $A(t)$: Requires longitudinal surveys or revealed preference data—challenging for bi-weekly resolution
- $Q(t)$: Accessibility calculation possible but data-intensive (census + full transit schedules)
- $P(t)$: Dependent on operator cooperation for fare data
- $B(t)$: Requires app usage analytics or stated preference surveys—labor intensive

Aspirational indicators (low feasibility, <30% confidence):

- $E_{\text{energy}}(t)$: Requires utility partnership and SCADA access
- $E_{\text{ICT}}(t)$: Requires telecom operator cooperation

Tiered implementation strategy:

1. **Minimal viable model:** Core indicators only (M , R , C , D_{eff} , S , I) with simplified target function
2. **Standard model:** Core + Q and P indicators (if accessible)
3. **Full model:** All 12 indicators as specified

Cities should begin with the minimal viable model and expand as data partnerships mature. The framework's mathematical structure accommodates indicator subsets by re-normalizing weights within available categories.

5 The Antifragile Urban Mobility Target-Setting Model

This section presents the strategic core of the antifragile mobility framework, detailing how post-shock learning is formalized through the Target-Setting Model to define improved system performance targets. We formalize how disruptions raise targets and how performance relaxes toward them.

5.1 Model Philosophy and Role

We now make this philosophy operational via a simple convergence law. The Target-Setting Model serves as the strategic "brain" of the antifragile mobility system. Its primary function is to learn from disruptions and establish improved performance targets that guide the system toward antifragile states. Unlike reactive models that merely restore pre-disruption conditions, this model actively seeks to identify opportunities for permanent improvement embedded within shock events.

The model operates on the principle that disruptions, while initially harmful, can reveal system weaknesses, activate capacities unexplored before, and trigger innovations that lead to superior equilibrium states. By quantifying this "gain-from-disorder" through the Antifragility Factor (AF), the model provides a formal mechanism for validating whether observed improvements are statistically significant and operationally meaningful. We then introduce the convergence equation that steers performance toward targets.

5.2 Core Dynamical Equation

This dynamics depends on the target function, which we decompose next. The antifragile potential $E(t)$ is an aggregate KPI $\bar{E}(x)$ per period, evolving via relaxation:

$$\dot{E} = -\kappa (E - \bar{E}(x))$$

Note: This is a convergence model, not an equilibrium model in the Wardrop sense. The relaxation equation is adapted from control theory and dynamical systems, commonly used in resilience studies. From the 123-study review, we synthesized indicators that affect system performance into the target function $\bar{E}(x)$.

5.3 Target Performance Function

Here we decompose the target into positive and negative blocks and show its range. The target performance is structured as a weighted combination of positive and negative components:

$$\bar{E}(x) = \lambda \bar{E}^+(x) - (1 - \lambda) \bar{E}^-(x), \quad \lambda \in (0, 1),$$

$$\text{Range: } \bar{E} \in [\lambda - 1, \lambda]$$

$$\text{Normalisation: } \bar{E}_{\text{target}} = \bar{E} - \lambda + 1$$

where:

$$\bar{E}^+(x) = \alpha_1 M + \alpha_2 R + \alpha_3 A + \alpha_4 H_{\text{norm}} + \omega_1 E_{\text{energy}} + \omega_2 E_{\text{ICT}} + \zeta I + \pi P + \mu B,$$

$$\bar{E}^-(x) = \beta_1 D_{\text{eff}} + \beta_2 S + \theta Q.$$

5.4 Information Entropy Indicator Specification

We define topology-aware entropy and explain why normalization matters under disruption. $C(t)$ denotes the information entropy of the origin–destination (OD) flow distribution, measuring how evenly trips are distributed across OD pairs (each OD pair = one ordered origin–destination cell in the OD matrix).

$$\psi(C) = H_{\text{norm}}, \quad H_{\text{norm}} = \frac{C}{C_{\text{max}}(\text{current_topology})},$$

where C is Shannon entropy (C in nats).

Maximum information entropy. We assume a uniform distribution across all accessible OD pairs. With N_{OD} accessible pairs:

$$C_{\text{max}}(\text{current topology}) = - \sum_{i=1}^{N_{OD}} \left[\frac{1}{N_{OD}} \times \ln\left(\frac{1}{N_{OD}}\right) \right] = \ln(N_{OD}).$$

This simplification arises because under uniform distribution each OD pair has probability $p_i = \frac{1}{N_{OD}}$, yielding:

$$C_{\text{max}} = -N_{OD} \times \left(\frac{1}{N_{OD}} \ln\left(\frac{1}{N_{OD}}\right) \right) = \ln(N_{OD}).$$

Example: With 90 accessible OD pairs under uniform distribution,

$$C_{\text{max}} = \ln(90) \approx 4.50 \text{ nats.}$$

Why topology changes affect normalization. When network disruption reduces accessible OD pairs (e.g., from 90 to 70), the maximum possible information entropy decreases from $\ln(90)$ to $\ln(70)$. This ensures that our normalized metric

$$H_{\text{norm}} = \frac{C}{C_{\text{max}}}$$

reflects genuine flow diversity relative to what is currently possible, rather than an artificially deflated value compared to the pre-disruption network.

Alternative Information Entropy Efficiency Measure. An alternative normalization approach uses *information entropy efficiency* (following Stan's `posterior` package methodology):

$$H_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\exp(H)}{N},$$

where H is the Shannon entropy and N is the number of possible outcomes (OD pairs).

This measure:

- Ranges from $1/N$ (minimum, all mass on one outcome) to 1 (maximum, uniform distribution).
- Has intuitive interpretation: the effective proportion of outcomes being used.
- Remains in nats as the underlying unit.

Comparison with our approach.

- Our method: $H_{\text{norm}} = H/H_{\text{max}} = H/\ln(N)$, range $[0, 1]$.
- Efficiency method: $H_{\text{eff}} = \exp(H)/N$, range $[1/N, 1]$.

Both are valid. We chose H/H_{max} for:

1. Consistent $[0, 1]$ range regardless of N .
2. Linear relationship with raw information entropy.
3. Direct interpretability as “percentage of maximum possible information entropy.”

Cities may adopt the efficiency measure if preferred, adjusting α_4 accordingly to maintain comparable influence in the target function $\bar{E}(x)$.

5.5 Parameter Specification

We list initial parameter values and normalization conventions.

```

1 {
2   "alpha_1": 0.25, "alpha_2": 0.25, "alpha_3": 0.25, "alpha_4": 0.25,
3   "beta_1": 0.57, "beta_2": 0.43,
4   "omega_1": 0.5, "omega_2": 0.5,
5   "zeta": 0.1, "theta": 0.1, "pi": 0.1,
6   "chi": 1.0,
7   "kappa": 0.1,
8   "delta_transport": 1.0, "delta_environment_weather": 0.9,
9   "delta_utilities": 0.9, "delta_social": 0.9,
10  "tau_days": 6,
11  "omega_src_official": 1.0, "omega_src_operator": 0.9,
12  "omega_src_sensor": 0.9, "omega_src_social": 0.6,
13  "omega_src_survey": 0.6,
14  "mu": 0.15, "lambda": 0.70
15 }
```

Notation: ω_1, ω_2 are infrastructure weights (energy, ICT). ω_{src} refers to source reliability weights in the disturbance mapping. These are unrelated.

Weight sets are normalized to sum to 1.0 within each category:

$$\sum \alpha = 1, \quad \sum \beta = 1, \quad \sum \omega = 1.$$

Given parameters, we state the discrete update used in computation.

5.6 Discrete Update Rule

We provide the computational update and interpret its timescale.

Notation convention. Throughout this document, we use $E(t)$ for continuous-time conceptual formulations and E_k (or E_t in discrete context) for computational implementations. In the Learning Model, time t refers to periods (days), while in Algorithm 1, k denotes iteration count within the equilibrium solver. Both represent the same performance measure at different temporal resolutions.

With $\kappa = 0.1$ (as documented in the parameter table; typical convergence in ~ 10 periods), the discrete update rule is:

$$E_{t+1} = E_t - \kappa (E_t - \bar{E}(x_t)).$$

Each city has a unique Target-Setting Model and equilibrium based on topology, demand patterns, and infrastructure. **Note on convergence timescales.** In first-order linear systems $\dot{E} = -\kappa(E - \bar{E})$, the characteristic timescale is $\tau = 1/\kappa$. With $\kappa = 0.1$, we have $\tau = 10$ periods, meaning the system closes $1 - e^{-1} \approx 63\%$ of the initial gap in 10 periods. Full convergence (95% of gap closed) requires approximately $3\tau \approx 30$ periods. When we state "convergence in ~ 10 periods," we refer to the dominant time constant τ , not complete stabilization. This is standard control theory notation where the time constant characterizes system responsiveness.

5.7 Worked Example

A concise numeric example illustrates the update mechanics. Suppose the baseline performance is $E_0 = 0.60$, the recovery target is $\bar{E} = 0.67$ (raised, in part, due to high diversity reflected in $\psi(C) = 0.75$), and $\kappa = 0.1$. The first update step is:

$$E_1 = E_0 - \kappa (E_0 - \bar{E}) = 0.60 - 0.1 (0.60 - 0.67) = 0.60 - 0.1 \times (-0.07) = 0.607.$$

Thus the system moves 10% of the way from the current state (0.60) toward the target (0.67). Repeated iterations converge monotonically to \bar{E} , as $|1 - \kappa| = 0.9 < 1$ ensures stability.

5.8 Calibration Protocol

We outline expert-plus-data calibration and correlation-matrix safeguards.

- Two-stage: (1) AHP expert elicitation (e.g., 20 scholars / 10 practitioners) for relative weights. (2) Elastic-net regression on 2019–2025 events to maximise out-of-sample R^2 on ΔE . Preliminary 0.6/0.4 weighting (expert-favored pending sufficient data); ratio will be cross-validated in Phase 2. Also, these coefficients depend on data quality and sample size; higher values when data are sparse.
- Final weights as a convex combination: 0.6 expert + 0.4 data (document ranges and cross-validated λ).
- Implementation: Python; dynamics via a discrete update; archive code and seeds.

Correlation Matrix Projection: If pilot data yields a non-positive-semidefinite correlation matrix:

1. Apply Higham [32] nearest correlation matrix projection.
2. Preserve diagonal elements (all = 1.0).
3. Minimize Frobenius norm of correction.
4. Verify all eigenvalues ≥ 0 in the corrected matrix.
5. Document any significant changes from theoretical expectations.

5.9 Calibration of κ

We explain how adjustment speed is tuned by context and evidence. The adjustment speed κ is NOT fixed but calibrated for each city based on:

- Historical recovery data (primary method)
- System type (transport: 0.2-0.3, infrastructure: 0.05-0.1)
- Event severity (major disruptions may temporarily reduce κ)

κ is recalibrated annually or after major events. Cities start with $\kappa = 0.1$ and adjust based on observed convergence rates.

5.10 Disturbance Calculation from D2.1 Event Catalogue

We derive D_{eff} from event attributes, recency, and sources. For an event e with domain d , severity level $L \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$, start time t_e , and source type src , define

$$D_{\text{eff}}(e, t) = \omega_{\text{src}}(\text{src}) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{t-t_e}{\tau}\right) \cdot \delta_d \cdot \frac{L-1}{4}.$$

Aggregate across concurrent events:

$$D_{\text{eff}}(t) = \sum_e D_{\text{eff}}(e, t).$$

Here $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$ replaces raw disturbance terms and co-varies with $S(t)$ computed on links within the event's area(s) of interest (AOIs).

Severity assignment protocol. Severity levels L are assigned to disruption types from the D2.1 event ontology based on: (i) duration impact (hours of network degradation); (ii) spatial extent (percentage of network affected); (iii) cascading potential (likelihood of secondary effects). The mapping from disruption types to L values will be established through systematic literature review in Phase 2, creating a reference table ((e.g., major flood = $L4$ or $L5$, arterial crash = $L1$ or $L2$, metro closure = $L3$ or $L4$)) to ensure consistent encoding across cities.

Scale and Magnitude Guidelines

- Individual events: $D_{\text{eff}}(e, t) \in [0, 1]$ (severity $L = 5$, immediate, reliable source).
- Typical magnitudes:
 - Minor ($L = 1-2$): 0.1–0.3,
 - Major ($L = 4-5$): 0.5–0.8.
- Multiple concurrent events:

$$D_{\text{eff}}(t) = \sum D_{\text{eff}}(e, t)$$

with soft cap at 1.0:

$$D_{\text{eff,final}} = \min(1.0, D_{\text{eff,raw}}) \quad \text{or use softplus: } \ln(1 + e^{D_{\text{eff,raw}}}).$$

We operationalize AF, thresholds, and windows for validation.

5.11 Antifragility Factor Definition

The Antifragility Factor quantifies post-disruption improvement:

Let E_{base} be the seasonally-adjusted baseline mean over a pre-event window. Define the post-event 30-day mean

$$\mu_{30} = \frac{1}{30} \sum_{t=31}^{60} E(t), \quad \text{AF} = \frac{\mu_{30}}{E_{\text{base}}}.$$

We use two thresholds and decide by the maximum:

$$AF_{\text{req}} = 1 + 0.2(1 - E_{\text{base}}), \quad AF_{\text{crit}} = 1 + \delta, \quad \delta = k \hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}},$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ is the standard deviation of pre-event residuals after Seasonal and Trend decomposition using Loess (STL) [33], and k sets confidence (default $k = 1.64$ for 95% one-sided). We declare AF if

$$\textbf{Decision:} \quad \text{AF if } \text{LCL}_{0.95}(\text{AF}) \geq \max\{AF_{\text{req}}, AF_{\text{crit}}\}.$$

Parameter justification. The 30-day stabilization window balances two requirements: sufficient observations for statistical power ($n \geq 30$ for CLT approximation) and timely validation (monthly operational cycles). The coefficient 0.2 in $AF_{\text{req}} = 1 + 0.2(1 - E_{\text{base}})$ reflects diminishing returns: systems near optimal performance ($E_{\text{base}} \approx 1$) require minimal improvement ($AF \approx 1.0$), while degraded systems ($E_{\text{base}} = 0.5$) must demonstrate 10% gain ($AF \geq 1.10$). This linear interpolation is a first approximation pending empirical validation in Phase 2.

Extended assessment for severe disruptions. For high-severity events ($L=4-5$) where recovery extends beyond the standard 60-day period, the stabilization window may be extended with documented justification. In such cases, calculate both:

1. **Short-term AF** (days 31-60): Captures immediate post-recovery state and emergency adaptations
2. **Long-term AF** (days 91-120 or 181-210): Validates persistence of improvements and distinguishes temporary emergency measures from permanent structural gains

Antifragility is confirmed only if both phases satisfy AF thresholds, ensuring observed improvements are stable rather than transient emergency responses. The extended window requires additional seasonal adjustment (STL decomposition over 12+ months pre-event) and explicit documentation of confounding factors. This severity-gated approach maintains the framework's standard protocol for moderate disruptions while providing flexibility for rare catastrophic events, though validation remains limited by data availability and attribution challenges for black swan scenarios.

5.12 Statistical Validation Protocol

We close with confidence intervals, stability checks, and change detection.

Confidence interval for the ratio. Compute a one-sided 95% lower confidence limit $LCL_{0.95}(AF)$ using either:

1. *Bootstrap (recommended)*: block bootstrap daily values in both windows and form the percentile lower bound of AF (preserves autocorrelation); or
2. *Delta method*: approximate $\text{Var}(AF)$ from window variances and apply a one-sided normal CI when independence and homoscedasticity are plausible.

10-day stability test. Require convergence within noise in the final 10 days of the 30-day window:

$$|E(t) - \mu_{30}| < 2\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}} \quad \text{for all } t \in [51, 60].$$

As a robustness check, report the maximum absolute Cumulative Sum control chart for change detection (CUSUM) [34] over $t \in [31, 60]$ and confirm it lies below the 95% control bound.

Note. The 30-day window for computing μ_{30} begins after the acute disruption phase ends (typically days 31–60 post-event), ensuring we measure the new equilibrium state rather than transient disruption effects. For information entropy $C(t)$, this captures whether learned diversity persists, not temporary forced dispersion.

6 The Three-Layer Equilibrium Model

This section describes how the equilibrium mechanism operationalizes antifragility through three coupled layers: traffic flow, modal choice, and system learning that translate target performance into adaptive network behavior.

6.1 Model Philosophy and Role

The Three-Layer Equilibrium Model serves as the operational "body" that implements the strategic targets set by the Target-Setting Model. While the Target-Setting Model identifies *what* performance level should be achieved post-disruption, this model specifies *how* the system can structurally evolve to reach that target through three integrated equilibrium layers:

1. **Layer 1 (Traffic Flow):** Wardrop user equilibrium ensuring efficient route distribution
2. **Layer 2 (Modal Split):** Discrete choice equilibrium balancing mode preferences
3. **Layer 3 (System Learning):** Causal learning mechanism that embeds validated improvements into network structure

The model uses the System Responsiveness Index (SRI) to guide adaptive capacity adjustments and an Antifragility Gate to ensure only statistically validated improvements become permanent.

6.2 Notation and Dimensional Consistency

Key symbols and units are summarized for clarity.

Table 3: Symbol Glossary for Equilibrium Model

Symbol	Definition	Unit
$\mathbf{c}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{ A }$	Network capacity vector at time t	veh/h
$\mathbf{f}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{ A }$	Link flow vector	veh/h
$\mathbf{m}_t \in [0, 1]^{ M }$	Modal split vector	proportion
$\mathbf{g}_{\text{short}}$	Short-term adaptation vector	[-0.5, 0.5]
\mathbf{g}_{long}	Long-term change vector	[-0.2, 0.2]
ε_{ops}	Operational elasticity	[0,1]
ρ_{infra}	Infrastructure pressure	[0,1]
L_{index}	Learning index	[-1,1]
$\eta_s = 0.1$	Short-term learning rate	per iteration
$\eta_\ell = 0.01$	Long-term learning rate	per iteration
$\tau_L = 30$	Memory decay constant	days
$\theta = 0.1$	Logit scale parameter [35]	dimensionless
$\lambda = 0.7$	Performance weight	dimensionless
\odot	Element-wise multiplication	-
$\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$	Indicator function	{0,1}

6.3 Hierarchical Solution Algorithm

We present the overall loop and cross-layer consistency check. The three-layer equilibrium is solved through a hierarchical update loop with temporal resolution of 15 minutes during events, daily otherwise.

$$\text{CrossLayerConsistency}(f, m) = \max_{od} | \text{flow_share}_{od} - \text{mode_share}_{od} |$$

Figure 2: High-level overview of the hierarchical antifragile equilibrium solution process. The Target-Setting Model (Phase 2) computes both realized performance E_k and target \bar{E}_k ; the Antifragility Gate (Phase 3) validates long-term changes before embedding; detailed convergence criteria are specified in Algorithm 1.

We solve Wardrop user equilibrium with standard cost functions

Algorithm 1 Hierarchical Antifragile Equilibrium Solution

```

1: Initialize:  $\mathbf{c}_0, E_0, k = 0, \max\_iter = 1000$ 
2: Set tolerances:  $\varepsilon_1 = 10^{-3}, \varepsilon_2 = 10^{-3}, \varepsilon_3 = 10^{-4}, \varepsilon_4 = 10^{-2}, \varepsilon_5 = 0.05$ 
3: repeat
4:   Phase 1: Solve User Equilibrium given  $\mathbf{c}_k$ 
5:     Layer 1:  $\mathbf{f}_k = \text{Wardrop}(\mathbf{c}_k, \mathbf{q})$  {Traffic flows}
6:     Layer 2:  $\mathbf{m}_k = \text{ModalSplit}(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{U})$  {Mode shares}
7:   Phase 2: Evaluate Performance
8:     Calculate KPIs:  $\mathbf{x}_k = \text{ComputeKPIs}(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{m}_k)$ 
9:      $E_k = E(\mathbf{x}_k)$  via performance function (Section 5.3, applied to realized KPIs)
10:     $\bar{E}_k = \bar{E}(\mathbf{x}_k)$  via target function (Section 5.3)
11:   Phase 3: System Learning
12:     Update weights:  $\mathbf{w}_k = \text{UpdateWeights}(\mathbf{w}_{k-1}, \text{errors}_{k-1})$ 
13:      $\text{SRl}_k = w_1(k)\varepsilon_{\text{ops}}(k) + w_2(k)\rho_{\text{infra}}(k) + w_3(k)L_{\text{index}}(k)$ 
14:      $\mathbf{g}_{\text{short}}(k) = \nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \bar{E}_k \cdot \mathbb{I}[\text{temporary}]$ 
15:      $\mathbf{g}_{\text{long}}(k) = \mathbf{g}_{\text{short}}(k - \tau) \cdot \mathbb{I}[\text{AFGate}]$ 
16:   Phase 4: Network Update with Line Search
17:      $\alpha = 1.0$ 
18:
19:   while  $E(\mathbf{c}_k + \alpha \Delta \mathbf{c}) < E(\mathbf{c}_k) + 0.5\alpha \nabla E^T \Delta \mathbf{c}$  do
20:      $\alpha = 0.5\alpha$ 
21:
22:   end while
23:    $\mathbf{c}_{k+1} = \Pi_{\mathcal{C}}\{\mathbf{c}_k \odot [1 + \alpha(\eta_s \mathbf{g}_{\text{short}}(k) + \eta_\ell \mathbf{g}_{\text{long}}(k))]\}$ 
24:    $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
25: until  $\|\mathbf{f}_k - \mathbf{f}_{k-1}\|_2 < \varepsilon_1$  AND  $\|\mathbf{m}_k - \mathbf{m}_{k-1}\|_2 < \varepsilon_2$ 
      AND  $\|\mathbf{c}_k - \mathbf{c}_{k-1}\|_\infty < \varepsilon_3$  AND  $|E_k - E_{k-1}| < \varepsilon_4$  for 5 periods
      AND  $\text{CrossLayerConsistency}(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{m}_k) < \varepsilon_5$  OR  $k > \max\_iter$ 

```

6.4 Layer 1: Traffic Flow Equilibrium

The traffic equilibrium follows Wardrop's First Principle with polynomial cost functions:

$$\min_{\mathbf{f}} Z(\mathbf{f}) = \sum_{a \in A} \int_0^{f_a} t_a(\omega) d\omega \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{p \in P_{rs}} h_p^{rs} = q_{rs}, \quad \forall (r, s) \in W \quad (2)$$

$$f_a = \sum_{(r,s) \in W} \sum_{p \in P_{rs}} h_p^{rs} \delta_{ap}^{rs}, \quad \forall a \in A \quad (3)$$

$$h_p^{rs} \geq 0, \quad \forall p \in P_{rs}, \forall (r, s) \in W \quad (4)$$

where the link cost function is:

$$t_a(f_a) = t_a^0 \left[1 + 0.15 \left(\frac{f_a}{c_a} \right)^4 \right] \quad (5)$$

with t_a^0 the free-flow travel time (minutes), c_a the capacity (veh/h), satisfying:

- Continuity: $t_a(\cdot)$ is C^1
- Monotonicity: $t'_a(f) > 0$ for $f > 0$
- Boundedness: Under the feasibility constraint $f_a \leq 3c_a$ (implicit in traffic management), $t_a(f) \leq 10 \cdot t_a^0$

Link cost function. We adopt the standard Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) cost function [36] with calibrated parameters $\alpha = 0.15$ and $\beta = 4$, widely used in traffic assignment models. The exponent $\beta = 4$ produces the characteristic sharp increase in travel time as flow approaches capacity, while $\alpha = 0.15$ reflects the ratio of congested-to-free-flow time at capacity. Alternative formulations (e.g., Davidson $\beta = 2$) exist but BPR remains the benchmark for urban networks.

Methodological choice: Deterministic vs. stochastic assignment. We adopt deterministic Wardrop equilibrium rather than stochastic user equilibrium (e.g., multinomial logit-based assignment) for computational tractability in the three-layer framework. Stochastic assignment could be incorporated in future extensions to capture perception errors and heterogeneous value-of-time, particularly if pilot data reveal significant route choice variability unexplained by travel time alone.

6.5 Layer 2: Modal Split Equilibrium

We allocate demand across modes via discrete choice.

Why separate modal equilibrium? Wardrop equilibrium (Layer 1) addresses route choice within modes but does not determine modal split. The nested logit model (Layer 2) is necessary because:

1. Mode choice involves discrete alternatives with different cost structures (time, money, comfort)
2. Capacity constraints interact differently across modes (road capacity vs. transit capacity)
3. Antifragile adaptations often involve modal shifts (e.g., temporary bus lanes, bike-sharing expansion)
4. Without Layer 2, the model cannot capture policies like pricing or service changes that primarily affect mode choice rather than route choice

Cities may simplify to fixed modal split if mode choice is not a policy lever, but this reduces the framework's ability to identify antifragile modal rebalancing opportunities.

The modal choice follows a multinomial logit (MNL) model [37] with scale parameter $\theta = 0.1$:

$$P_i^m = \frac{\exp(-\theta U_i^m)}{\sum_{m' \in M} \exp(-\theta U_i^{m'})} \quad (6)$$

where the generalized cost is:

$$U_i^m = 0.5 \cdot t_i^m + 0.3 \cdot c_i^m + 0.2 \cdot \xi_i^m + \varepsilon_i^m \quad (7)$$

with t_i^m in minutes, c_i^m in euros, $\xi_i^m \in [0, 10]$ comfort score, and $\varepsilon_i^m \sim \text{Gumbel}(0,1)$.

Utility function specification. The generalized cost weights (0.5 time, 0.3 monetary, 0.2 comfort) reflect typical European value-of-time estimates where time is weighted 1.5-2× monetary cost [38]. The logit scale parameter $\theta = 0.1$ corresponds to moderate sensitivity to utility differences; lower values ($\theta \rightarrow 0$) imply deterministic choice, higher values ($\theta \rightarrow \infty$) approach uniform randomness. City-specific calibration (Phase 2) will refine these parameters using revealed preference data from smart-card traces.

6.6 Layer 3: The System Responsiveness Index (SRI)

We combine operational elasticity, infrastructure pressure, and learning into a single driver.

6.6.1 SRI Components

$$\text{SRI}(t) = w_1(t) \cdot \varepsilon_{\text{ops}}(t) + w_2(t) \cdot \rho_{\text{infra}}(t) + w_3(t) \cdot L_{\text{index}}(t) \quad (8)$$

Rationale and adaptive weighting mechanism. The SRI combines three distinct capacity-adjustment drivers: *operational elasticity* (ε_{ops}) measures immediate flexibility from redundancy and stress; *infrastructure pressure* (ρ_{infra}) captures cumulative strain and equity concerns; and *causal learning index* (L_{index}) provides evidence-based guidance from validated past interventions. These three were selected because capacity adjustments must balance immediate feasibility, long-term sustainability, and empirical validation—other KPIs (M, R, A, C) are performance outcomes that inform the target $\bar{E}(x)$ rather than operational adjustment mechanisms.

The component weights w_1, w_2, w_3 adapt based on predictive accuracy: each component generates a one-step-ahead forecast of system performance $E(t+1)$ using simple regression on recent data, denoted $\text{predicted}_i(t)$ for component i . The "actual" value is the subsequently observed $E(t+1)$. Components with smaller forecast errors receive higher weights in the SRI, ensuring the mechanism favors currently-relevant factors as system conditions evolve.

Weight Dynamics. Weights evolve via exponential moving average of component forecast errors:

$$e_i(t) = |\text{predicted}_i(t-1) - E(t)| \quad (\text{forecast error for component } i) \quad (9)$$

$$r_i(t) = \frac{1}{1 + e_i(t)} \quad (\text{reliability}) \quad (10)$$

$$w_i(t) = \frac{r_i(t)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 r_j(t)} \quad (\text{normalized weight}) \quad (11)$$

Updated daily with smoothing factor $\alpha_w = 0.95$:

$$w_i(t) = \alpha_w w_i(t-1) + (1 - \alpha_w) \frac{r_i(t)}{\sum_j r_j(t)} \quad (12)$$

Operational Elasticity.

$$\varepsilon_{\text{ops}}(t) = \frac{R(t) \cdot (1 - S(t))}{1 + \exp(-10(R(t) - 0.2))} \quad (13)$$

Infrastructure Pressure.

$$\rho_{\text{infra}}(t) = \int_{t-T_{\text{infra}}}^t \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{\tau_l}\right) \cdot [S(\tau) + 0.3Q(\tau)] d\tau \quad (14)$$

where T_{infra} is the integration window and $\tau_l = 30$ days is the memory decay constant.

Dynamic window specification. The integration window T_{infra} adapts to the temporal scale of infrastructure effects:

- **Default (operational stress):** $T_{\text{infra}} = 90$ days ($3 \times \tau_l$), capturing quarterly operational cycles and near-term congestion impacts. The exponential weighting ensures 95% of pressure comes from the most recent 90 days.
- **Extended (structural degradation):** $T_{\text{infra}} = 180$ –365 days for assessment of long-term infrastructure fatigue, pavement degradation, or persistent equity impacts. Longer windows capture cumulative effects that manifest over multiple seasons.
- **Continuous monitoring protocol:** Rather than fixed windows, implement rolling assessment with monthly re-evaluation of $\rho_{\text{infra}}(t)$ to detect emerging long-term trends. If month-over-month change $|\Delta\rho| > 0.05$ persists for 3+ months, extend T_{infra} and investigate structural causes.

The choice of T_{infra} depends on the decision context: operational capacity adjustments use 90-day windows for responsiveness; strategic infrastructure investment uses 6–12 month windows for comprehensive assessment. The exponential decay weighting ($e^{-(t-\tau)/\tau_l}$) ensures recent stress dominates regardless of window length, preventing dilution from distant history while maintaining sensitivity to persistent trends.

Rationale for baseline 90-day window: This represents $3 \times \tau_l$, which captures 95% of the exponentially-weighted pressure ($1 - e^{-3} \approx 0.95$). Extending to 180 days ($6 \times \tau_l$) adds only 0.2% more weight, providing diminishing returns for operational decisions. However, for equity analysis where effects compound slowly, longer windows (180–365 days) are appropriate and should be used when assessing persistent distributional impacts.

SRI parameter specification. The sigmoid steepness factor 10 in ε_{ops} creates a sharp transition at redundancy threshold $R = 0.2$, below which operational flexibility degrades rapidly. The 90-day integration window for ρ_{infra} captures infrastructure fatigue over quarterly cycles, longer than the 30-day performance window to reflect slower degradation processes. The equity weight 0.3 in the stress term reflects observed correlations between congestion and accessibility inequality. These are initial specifications pending sensitivity analysis and city-specific calibration in Phase 2.

6.6.2 The Causal Learning Index

We quantify evidence from interventions and patterns to guide durable changes.

$$L_{\text{index}}(t) = \alpha_{\text{trace}} \cdot L_{\text{trace}}(t) + \alpha_{\text{pattern}} \cdot L_{\text{pattern}}(t) \quad (15)$$

Initially $\alpha_{\text{trace}} = 0.8$, $\alpha_{\text{pattern}} = 0.2$, evolving as data accumulates.

The Causal Trace.

$$L_{\text{trace}}(t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \exp\left(-\frac{t - t_i}{\tau_i}\right) \cdot \text{Contribution}(i) \cdot \text{sgn}(\text{AF}_{\text{achieved}}(t_i) - 1) \quad (16)$$

where \mathcal{A} is the set of all discrete adaptations (e.g., signal timing changes, lane reconfigurations, fare adjustments) implemented during the observation period. For ties/noise: $\text{sgn}(x) = 0$ if $|x| < 0.01$.

Contribution weights use inverse-variance weighting:

$$w_{\text{SCM}} = \frac{1/\sigma_{\text{SCM}}^2}{1/\sigma_{\text{SCM}}^2 + 1/\sigma_{\text{ABL}}^2}, \quad w_{\text{ABL}} = \frac{1/\sigma_{\text{ABL}}^2}{1/\sigma_{\text{SCM}}^2 + 1/\sigma_{\text{ABL}}^2} \quad (17)$$

SCM Diagnostics. The Synthetic Control Method requires:

- Donor pool preregistration: Min 20 control units
- Pre-period RMSPE ratio: $\frac{\text{RMSPE}_{\text{post}}}{\text{RMSPE}_{\text{pre}}} > 2$ for significance
- In-space placebos: Effect rank ≥ 95 th percentile
- Balance table: Covariates within 0.25 SD

The Pattern Engine. Graph features: $\{f_a, c_a, S_a, \text{betweenness}_a\}$ for edges, $\{\text{degree}_v, \text{clustering}_v\}$ for nodes. Context vector: $\mathbf{z}_t = [D_{\text{eff}}(t), P(t), B(t), Q(t), \text{time-of-day}, \text{day-of-week}]^T$. Training: 70% train, 15% validation, 15% test split, with temporal ordering.

Equity Monotonicity. Enforced via monotone neural network layers:

$$h^{(\ell+1)} = \sigma\left(\mathbf{W}_+^{(\ell)} h^{(\ell)} - \mathbf{W}_-^{(\ell)} h_Q^{(\ell)}\right) \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_+ \geq 0$ for all features except Q , and $\mathbf{W}_- \geq 0$ for Q features only.

6.7 The Antifragile Update Mechanism

Short and long term capacity updates are applied under feasibility.

6.7.1 Two-Timescale Updates

The update mechanism operates on two distinct timescales to separate rapid responses from lasting structural changes. This subsection introduces the mathematical formulation that governs how short- and long-term adjustments co-evolve under antifragility constraints.

$$\mathbf{c}_{t+1} = \Pi_C \left\{ \mathbf{c}_t \odot [1 + \eta_s \mathbf{g}_{\text{short}}(t) + \eta_\ell \mathbf{g}_{\text{long}}(t)] \right\} \quad (19)$$

With $\eta_s = 0.1$, $\eta_\ell = 0.01$ (ratio = 10:1), and hysteresis deadband of 5% to prevent oscillation.

6.7.2 Feasible Set

To ensure updates remain physically and institutionally realistic, we restrict all capacity adjustments to a defined feasible set. The following conditions formalize the allowable region for budget, geometry, safety, and equity compliance. The projection set \mathcal{C} enforces:

$$\text{Budget: } \sum_a \text{cost}_a \cdot (c_a - c_a^0) \leq B_{\max} \quad (20)$$

$$\text{Geometry: } c_a \leq n_{\text{lanes},a} \cdot 2000 \text{ veh/h} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{Safety: } v_a/c_a \leq 0.95 \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Equity: } Q(t+1) - Q(t) \leq 0 \quad (23)$$

Feasibility checked via interior-point method with tolerance 10^{-6} .

6.8 The Antifragility Gate

Only statistically and causally validated improvements are promoted. Promotion criteria combining statistical and operational validation:

$$\text{Promote}(i) = \mathbb{I}[\text{Statistical}] \wedge \mathbb{I}[\text{Internal}] \wedge \mathbb{I}[\text{External}] \quad (24)$$

6.8.1 Statistical Validation

$$\text{LCL}_{0.95} \left(\frac{\mu_{30}^{\text{post}}}{\mu_{\text{base}}} \right) \geq \max\{\text{AF}_{\text{req}}, \text{AF}_{\text{crit}}\} \quad (25)$$

where:

- $\text{AF}_{\text{req}} = 1 + 0.2(1 - E_{\text{base}})$ (requirement-based threshold)
- $\text{AF}_{\text{crit}} = 1 + k \cdot \hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ (statistical threshold)
 - $k = 1.64$ for 95% confidence (default) or $k = 2.58$ for 99% confidence
- $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ estimation procedure:
 - Test residual distribution (Shapiro-Wilk if $n < 2000$, Kolmogorov-Smirnov otherwise)
 - If normal ($p > 0.05$): use $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ from STL decomposition
 - If non-normal: use robust estimator ($\text{MAD} \times 1.4826$) or bootstrap
- CI computation: block bootstrap with block size = 5 days, 10,000 resamples

6.8.2 Internal Validation

Precision/Recall $\geq 80\%$ for top- k causal factors ($k = 3$) against SCM ground truth.

6.8.3 External Validation

Leave-one-out cross-validation shows:

$$\Pr(\text{AF} > \tau | \text{model recommends}) > \Pr(\text{AF} > \tau | \text{baseline}) \quad (26)$$

6.9 Operational Framework

This subsection outlines how validated model outcomes are operationalized through structured decision processes that respect data quality, confidence levels, and institutional readiness.

6.9.1 Three-Tier Decision System

Decision authority is distributed across automated, guided, and exploratory tiers, ensuring that antifragile interventions are applied with the appropriate level of human oversight and confidence.

Table 4: Operational Decision Tiers

Tier	Time	Authority	Confidence Required
Automated	0-15 min	System	> 0.9
Guided	15-60 min	Human approval	> 0.7
Exploratory	60+ min	Human decision	Any

6.9.2 Data Quality Weighting

Learning weight adjusted by data quality:

$$w_{\text{learn}} = w_{\text{base}} \cdot \text{DQ} \quad (27)$$

where:

$$\text{DQ} = 0.4 \cdot \text{completeness} + 0.4 \cdot \text{accuracy} + 0.2 \cdot \text{timeliness} \quad (28)$$

Data quality weighting. The weights prioritize completeness and accuracy (0.4 each) over timeliness (0.2), reflecting that missing or erroneous data degrade model reliability more severely than moderate delays. For real-time applications, weights may shift to emphasize timeliness. These are initial specifications subject to sensitivity analysis in operational deployment.

6.10 Convergence Properties

We state conditions for existence, uniqueness, and rate of convergence.

6.10.1 Existence and Uniqueness

Theorem 1. Given:

1. Link costs $t_a(\cdot) \in C^1$ with $t'_a(f) > 0$
2. Compact feasible set $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{c} : \mathbf{c}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{c} \leq \mathbf{c}_{\max}\}$
3. Bounded demands $\sum_{r,s} q_{rs} \leq Q_{\max}$

Then the three-layer equilibrium exists and is unique for strictly convex $t_a(\cdot)$.

6.10.2 Convergence Rate

Assumptions. The convergence analysis assumes:

1. The aggregate performance function $E(\mathbf{x})$ is twice continuously differentiable
2. Given convex $t_a(\cdot)$ and compact \mathcal{C} , the composite objective has bounded curvature: $\|\nabla^2 E\| \leq L$ for some $L > 0$

Theorem 2. With step sizes satisfying:

$$\eta_s < \frac{2}{L_{\max}(\nabla^2 E)}, \quad \eta_\ell < \frac{\eta_s}{10} \quad (29)$$

Where L_{\max} denotes the maximum eigenvalue. The algorithm converges at rate $O(1/k)$ where k is the iteration count.

6.11 Supply-Side Considerations

The model incorporates supply responses through the System Responsiveness Index rather than explicit operator equilibrium. This simplification is appropriate for publicly-operated European transit systems where:

- Service levels are determined by public service obligations
- Supply adjustments follow administrative rather than market processes
- Infrastructure investment follows political rather than profit dynamics

Future extensions could incorporate explicit operator equilibrium for contexts with significant private transport provision.

7 Integration of Learning and Equilibrium Models

We detail the feedback architecture linking the Target-Setting and Equilibrium models, showing how iterative learning refines equilibrium performance through continuous adaptation and validation..

7.1 Conceptual Integration

The two models operate in a hierarchical feedback loop:

1. **Target-Setting Model** observes system performance $E(t)$ and disruption impacts $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$
2. **Target-Setting Model** computes target performance $\bar{E}(x)$ incorporating lessons from past shocks within established disruption categories (D2.1). For unprecedented events outside historical experience, the model extrapolates from structurally similar disruption types, though validation confidence decreases for truly novel scenarios (black swan limitation acknowledged in Executive Summary section).
3. **Equilibrium Model** receives $\bar{E}(x)$ as a guiding objective
4. **Equilibrium Model Layer 3** uses SRI to identify structural changes that move toward $\bar{E}(x)$
5. **Antifragility Gate** validates whether proposed changes achieve $AF > \text{threshold}$
6. **Approved changes** are permanently embedded via long-term update g_{long}
7. **New equilibrium** (Layers 1-2) emerges with improved capacity c_{new}
8. **Target-Setting Model** observes new $E(t)$ and updates baseline, enhancing system capacity for future disruptions regardless of whether they are expected or unprecedented.

This creates a learning loop where each validated shock improvement raises the system's baseline performance and resilience.

Generalization and transfer learning. The framework's ability to benefit from future disruptions, including those not yet experienced, relies on two mechanisms: (i) **within-category generalization**, where lessons from one capacity-reduction event (e.g., 30% closure) inform response to different magnitudes (50% closure); and (ii) **cross-category transfer**, where structural improvements (increased redundancy R , enhanced entropy C) provide robustness across diverse disruption types. However, this generalization capacity has limits: black swan events that fall entirely outside the D2.1 disruption ontology may require human-guided exploratory interventions (three-tier decision system, Section 6.9.1) rather than automated learning. The framework thus builds *general adaptive capacity* rather than preparing for specific known scenarios, though effectiveness decreases for disruptions with no structural similarity to historical experience.

7.2 Temporal Coordination

We align processes across their operating timescales. The models operate on different timescales:

Table 5: Model Timescales

Process	Timescale	Model Component
KPI monitoring	Hourly to daily	Target-Setting Model: Indicators
Traffic equilibrium	15 minutes (events) to daily	Equilibrium: Layer 1
Modal equilibrium	Daily	Equilibrium: Layer 2
Target convergence	10 periods (~10 days)	Target-Setting Model: κ update
SRI weight update	Daily	Equilibrium: Layer 3
Short-term adaptations	Days to weeks	Equilibrium: η_s
AF validation window	30 days post-recovery	Both models
Long-term structural change	Months to years	Equilibrium: η_ℓ
Parameter recalibration	Annual	Target-Setting Model: Weights, κ

7.3 Information Flow

Inputs and outputs between layers are enumerated for implementation.

Target-Setting Model → Equilibrium:

- Target performance $\bar{E}(x_t)$
- KPI values $\mathbf{x}_t = [M, R, A, C, D_{\text{eff}}, S, Q, P, B, E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}, I]$
- AF validation results (pass/fail for Antifragility Gate)

Equilibrium → Target-Setting Model:

- Realized performance $E(t)$ from equilibrium state
- Network state $\mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{m}_t$
- Adaptation history from causal trace L_{trace}

In the next section, we show how both models contribute to AF testing using common criteria.

7.4 Shared Validation Framework

Both models contribute to antifragility validation:

Table 6: Shared Validation Components

Component	Target-Setting Model Role	Equilibrium Model Role
AF calculation	Computes μ_{30}/E_{base}	Provides realized $E(t)$
Statistical test	Determines $AF_{\text{req}}, AF_{\text{crit}}$	Inputs to Gate decision
Stability check	10-day convergence test	5-period equilibrium test
Causal attribution	Provides disruption context	SCM/ABL contribution analysis
Equity constraint	$Q(t)$ penalty in \bar{E}^-	Monotonicity constraint

8 Validation Criteria and Protocols

This section formalizes the quantitative and statistical procedures used to verify convergence, antifragility gains, and stability across all model layers before implementation.

8.1 Equilibrium Verification Criteria

We define objective tests for new equilibrium states. New equilibrium confirmed when:

1. **Convergence:** $|E(t) - E(t - 1)| < 0.01$ for 5 consecutive periods
2. **No drift:** Linear regression slope of $E(t) < 0.001$
3. **Indicator stability:**

$$\forall x_i : |x_i(t) - \text{mean}(x_i)| < 0.05 \times (\max(x_i) - \min(x_i)), \quad (30)$$

where $\max(x_i)$, $\min(x_i)$ are computed over the 30-day stability window.

4. **No active interventions** required to maintain performance
5. **Cross-layer consistency:** $\text{CrossLayerConsistency}(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{m}) < 0.05$

8.2 Antifragility Validation Protocol

We set the step-by-step procedure for confirming AF. Combining statistical and operational validation:

1. **Pre-event baseline:** 30-day average E_{base} with seasonal adjustment
2. **Disruption monitoring:** High-frequency (hourly) KPI tracking
3. **Recovery phase:** Daily measurements for 14 days post-event
4. **Stabilization window:** Days 31-60 post-event for μ_{30} calculation
5. **Statistical test:** $\text{LCL}_{0.95}(\text{AF}) \geq \max\{\text{AF}_{\text{req}}, \text{AF}_{\text{crit}}\}$
6. **Stability test:** $|E(t) - \mu_{30}| < 2\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ for $t \in [51, 60]$
7. **Causal validation:** Precision/Recall $\geq 80\%$ for top-3 factors
8. **Equity check:** $\Delta Q \leq 0$ maintained
9. **Long-term confirmation:** Monthly tracking for 6 months post-stabilization (M1-M6), with follow-up assessments at M12 and M18 to verify persistence of antifragile gains and detect potential regression to baseline

8.3 Performance Degradation Curve Validation

As a complementary validation approach focusing on traffic engineering outcomes:

Method: Subject the system to disruptions of increasing severity (e.g., 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% capacity reduction) and compare performance loss curves:

- **Baseline (business-as-usual):** Static traffic management with no adaptive learning
- **Antifragile framework:** Full three-layer equilibrium with capacity learning

Hypothesis: The baseline exhibits exponential performance degradation:

$$\Delta E_{\text{baseline}}(\text{severity}) \propto e^{\beta \cdot \text{severity}}$$

while the antifragile framework shows sub-linear degradation:

$$\Delta E_{\text{framework}}(\text{severity}) \propto \text{severity}^{\alpha}, \quad \alpha < 1$$

Validation criterion: For disruption severity $\geq 50\%$, the performance gap should satisfy:

$$\Delta E_{\text{baseline}} - \Delta E_{\text{framework}} > 0.15$$

indicating meaningful resilience benefit.

This approach complements the AF validation (Section 7.2) by testing robustness across disruption magnitudes rather than single-event recovery.

8.4 Back-Testing Framework for Future Phases

The back-testing procedures described in this section are theoretical specifications designed to demonstrate methodological readiness within Deliverable D2.3. No empirical calibration or pilot-network validation is expected at this stage. Practical execution, including dataset acquisition, benchmark experiments, and city-specific testing will occur under Work Package 2 (Task 2.2) and follow-on implementation activities in WP3 (Pilot Deployment and Validation). These steps fall beyond the remit of this proposal and are planned for subsequent project phases.

8.4.1 Scope and Datasets

This subsection specifies back-testing procedures for future implementation. Deliverable D2.3 is theoretical; no empirical calibration or pilot-network testing is performed at this stage. Execution is planned for the future Phase(Multi-City Validation), and is therefore outside the scope of this proposal.

Two complementary tracks are recommended for later phases:

1. **Benchmark-network experiments (no real data):** run the full pipeline on canonical networks (e.g., Sioux Falls) under stylised shocks (capacity drops, demand surges) to verify that UE/SO-consistent interventions lead to statistically significant antifragility (AF) detections ($p < 0.05$ for primary analysis, with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons if testing >5 scenarios)
2. **Synthetic back-tests:** generate demand/supply series with known ground-truth improvements; estimate $(\kappa, \sigma, \mathbf{w})$ on a training segment and validate out-of-sample detection power and false-positive control.

Planned dataset use (for later phases): Phase 2 will add: *City A / Event Type 1* for calibration and *City B / Event Type 2* for external validation (holdout).

8.4.2 Experimental Design (for later phases)

Calibrate → Validate. Calibrate parameters on Track T1/T2 or City A, then validate on a disjoint case (Track T1/T2 held-out scenarios or City B). Report predictions for AF and errors against observed AF decisions.

Ablation. Run a minimal ablation to quantify contribution to AF:

1. drop R (redundancy) only,
2. drop C (diversity/entropy) only,
3. drop both R and C .

Report the change in effect size and decision outcomes.

8.4.3 Seasonality, Lags, and Alignment (for later phases)

Apply consistent temporal alignment before computing $\bar{E}(x_t)$: daily aggregation for mixed-frequency inputs; carry-forward for weekly/monthly policy variables; and explicit lag structure where theoretically required. Perform seasonal adjustment on $E(t)$ and inputs prior to baseline estimation.

8.4.4 Sensitivity and Uncertainty (for later phases)

Report: (i) Sobol or Morris sensitivity of the AF decision to (κ, σ, w) and missing-data mechanisms; (ii) ablation deltas; (iii) coverage-weighted uncertainty where proxies/imputation are used.

8.4.5 Reporting (for later phases)

For each case (Track T1/T2 or City B), report:

1. $E_{\text{base}}, \mu_{30}, \text{AF}, \text{LCL}_{0.95}(\text{AF}), \max\{\text{AF}_{\text{req}}, \text{AF}_{\text{crit}}\}$, and the AF decision;
2. stability test outcome and CUSUM summary;
3. ablation results (decision flips and effect-size changes);
4. run-time and data coverage.

9 Sensitivity Analysis

We assess the robustness of model outcomes by quantifying how key parameters and indicators influence antifragility performance and equilibrium stability.

9.1 Sobol Global Sensitivity

We assess which parameters drive performance and settling time. Global sensitivity on mean E and settling time (time to $|E - \bar{E}| \leq 5\%$ of the initial gap).

First-order S_i measures individual impact; total-order S_{T_i} includes interactions.

Example placeholder results (replace with project-run outputs):

Metric	Top Parameters	Values
First-Order (mean E)	$K_R, R, \alpha_4, E_{ICT}, \alpha_3$	0.1260, 0.1223, 0.0759, 0.0371, 0.0307
Total-Order (mean E)	$K_R, R, \alpha_4, E_{ICT}, \alpha_3$	0.1614, 0.1573, 0.1035, 0.0564, 0.0482

First-Order (S_i):

- Fix parameter i at different values
- Let all other parameters vary randomly
- Calculate variance of output when i is fixed
- $S_i = (\text{Total variance} - \text{Variance when } i \text{ fixed}) / \text{Total variance}$

Total-Order (S_{T_i}):

- Let all parameters except i vary
- Calculate variance from i and its interactions
- $S_{T_i} = \text{Variance due to } i \text{ (including interactions)} / \text{Total variance}$

9.2 Indicator Correlations

We summarize expected KPI relationships to inform modeling choices.

Positive Correlations:

- $R \uparrow \Rightarrow C \uparrow$ (0.65): More redundancy enables flow diversity
- $I \uparrow \Rightarrow M \uparrow$ (0.45): Better integration increases throughput
- $P \uparrow \Rightarrow A \uparrow$ (0.55): Pricing drives adaptation

Negative Correlations:

- $D_{\text{eff}} \uparrow \Rightarrow M \downarrow$ (-0.70): Disruptions reduce throughput
- $S \uparrow \Rightarrow C \downarrow$ (-0.40): Conditional correlation, holds when stress causes bottlenecks that concentrate flows.
 - If stress is distributed across the network: $S \uparrow$ may coincide with $C \uparrow$ (dispersed congestion).
 - If stress triggers rerouting: initial $S \uparrow$ with $C \uparrow$, followed by stabilization.
 - Sign and magnitude depend on network topology and disruption type.
- $P \uparrow \Rightarrow Q \uparrow$ (-0.35): Pricing may hurt equity

Note: Correlation values shown are typical estimates from the literature review. Actual correlations should be calibrated per city.

9.3 Correlation Matrix Validation

We ensure numerical stability via Positive Semi-Definiteness checks and condition limits. The complete correlation matrix must be constructed and validated with:

- **Eigenvalues:** [computed from actual pilot data]
- **Condition number:** [must be < 1000 for numerical stability]
- **Positive semidefinite:** [verify all eigenvalues ≥ 0]

9.4 Multicollinearity Assessment

We monitor VIF to avoid unstable inference.

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) [39]:

$$\text{VIF} = \frac{1}{1 - R^2} \quad \text{for each indicator}$$

- $\text{VIF} > 5$ indicates problematic multicollinearity.

10 Implementation Specifications

This section translates the theoretical model into computational procedures, defining algorithmic requirements and pseudocode for practical execution in later phases.

10.1 Computational Requirements

We estimate complexity and wall-clock performance. For typical city (1000 nodes, 3000 links, 100 OD pairs, 4 modes):

- Layer 1: $O(3000^2 \cdot 100) = O(9 \times 10^8)$ operations
- Layer 2: $O(4 \cdot 1000) = O(4 \times 10^3)$ operations
- Layer 3: $O(1000 \cdot 3000 \cdot 10) = O(3 \times 10^7)$ operations (10-layer GNN)
- Wall clock: ~ 2 minutes/iteration on 8-core CPU with 32GB RAM

10.2 Implementation Pseudocode

We provide a concise, end-to-end algorithmic recipe. For each time step t :

1. Read inputs

$$x(t) = [M, R, A, C, D_{\text{eff}}, S, Q, P, E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}, I, B].$$

2. Compute positive and negative blocks

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{E}^+ &= \alpha_1 M + \alpha_2 R + \alpha_3 A + \alpha_4 H_{\text{norm}} \\ &\quad + \omega_1 E_{\text{energy}} + \omega_2 E_{\text{ICT}} + \zeta I + \pi P + \mu B, \\ \bar{E}^- &= \beta_1 D_{\text{eff}} + \beta_2 S + \theta Q, \\ H_{\text{norm}} &= \frac{C}{C_{\text{max}}(\text{current_topology})}. \end{aligned}$$

3. Compute bounded target

$$\bar{E} = \lambda \bar{E}^+ - (1 - \lambda) \bar{E}^-$$

4. Map to [0,1] range

$$E_{\text{target, normalized}} = E - \lambda + 1$$

5. Update performance (Target-Setting Model)

$$E \leftarrow E - \kappa (E - \bar{E}_{\text{bounded}}).$$

6. Solve traffic equilibrium (Layer 1)

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \text{Wardrop}(\mathbf{c}_t, \mathbf{q})$$

7. Solve modal split (Layer 2)

$$\mathbf{m}_t = \text{ModalSplit}(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{U})$$

8. Compute SRI (Layer 3)

$$\text{SRI}_t = w_1 \varepsilon_{\text{ops}} + w_2 \rho_{\text{infra}} + w_3 L_{\text{index}}$$

9. Update capacity if AF Gate passed

$$\mathbf{c}_{t+1} = \Pi_{\mathcal{C}} \{ \mathbf{c}_t \odot [1 + \eta_s \mathbf{g}_{\text{short}} + \eta_\ell \mathbf{g}_{\text{long}}] \}$$

10. Log $E, \bar{E}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{m}$, AF status for validation.

11 PESTLE Integration and Contextual Adaptation

This section translates high-level PESTLE factors into concrete levers within the framework feasibility constraints, validation gates, and decision tiers, so that contextual limits shape model behaviour rather than remain narrative background.

11.1 PESTLE Framework Mapping

We tie constraints to concrete model components.

Table 7: PESTLE Constraints and Model Components

PESTLE Factor	Constraint Type	Model Implementation
Political	Governance authority, stakeholder buy-in	Three-tier decision system (automated/guided/exploratory)
Economic	Budget limits, cost-benefit requirements	Feasible set \mathcal{C} budget constraint
Social	Equity, public acceptance	$Q(t)$ penalty, equity monotonicity, behavioral compliance $B(t)$
Technological	Data availability, system capabilities	Data quality weighting, tiered implementation
Legal	Privacy, procurement, compliance	GDPR protocol, k-anonymity, differential privacy
Environmental	Sustainability, emissions	Can be added to \bar{E}^+ as additional KPI

11.2 Task 2.2 Workshop Integration

The theoretical framework will be refined through Task 2.2 stakeholder workshops in each pilot city (Bratislava, Odessa, Larissa and AHEPA DemoSite in Thessaloniki). Workshop outputs will inform:

1. **Parameter prioritization:** Which KPIs are most critical for each city
2. **Weight elicitation:** AHP process for α, β, ω parameters
3. **Constraint specification:** City-specific feasibility bounds in \mathcal{C}
4. **Validation thresholds:** Acceptable AF levels and equity limits
5. **Data availability:** Identification of high/medium/low availability indicators
6. **Institutional readiness:** Mapping decision authority to three-tier system

12 Dependencies and Future Implementation

This section consolidates the practical enablers data, ethics, and institutional cooperation required to translate the theoretical framework into operational reality across project phases.

12.1 Critical Dependencies

Implementation success depends on coordinated progress across three domains: data accessibility, ethical compliance, and institutional alignment, each shaping model feasibility and governance readiness.

12.1.1 Data Access

Ensuring secure and continuous access to high-quality data streams is foundational for the practical deployment of the antifragile equilibrium framework.

Table 8: Data Dependencies by Priority

Priority	Data Type	Required For	Mitigation
Critical	Smart card/AFC	$M(t)$, mode shares	None - blocks implementation
Critical High	Traffic sensors Network topology	$S(t)$, flows All layers	Use CDR proxy OpenStreetMap sufficient
High Medium	Event logs SCADA	$D_{\text{eff}}(t)$ $E_{\text{energy}}(t)$	D2.1 catalogue Conservative default
Medium Low	Surveys Real-time ICT	$A(t)$, $B(t)$ $E_{\text{ICT}}(t)$	Carry-forward Operator bulletins

12.1.2 Ethics and Compliance

All model applications must comply with GDPR and ethical standards, prioritizing fairness, privacy, and inclusion across all participating cities.

- **GDPR compliance [40]:** Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) required
- **Anonymization:** k -anonymity ($k=5$) for individual-level data
- **Differential privacy:** $\epsilon \approx 0.1$ for aggregate statistics
- **Consent:** Opt-in for behavioral tracking ($B(t)$)
- **Data sharing:** EU-compliant portals only, anonymized samples

Vulnerable populations and digital exclusion. The framework’s reliance on digital data sources (smart cards, mobile apps, CDR) risks systematically excluding vulnerable-to-exclusion groups: elderly without smart-phones, low-income populations unable to afford smart passes, disabled individuals with accessibility needs not captured in standard KPIs, migrants using informal transport, and rural residents with sparse data coverage. Ethical implementation requires:

- **Representative data collection:** Supplement digital sources with manual surveys targeting non-digital populations; ensure $B(t)$ behavioral metrics don’t bias against technology-excluded groups; validate that smart-card penetration rates are stratified by demographic to identify coverage gaps.
- **Equity safeguards in adaptations:** The hard constraint $Q(t + 1) - Q(t) \leq 0$ provides quantitative protection, but qualitative assessment is also needed: pricing policies $P(t)$ must include affordability analysis; service changes must maintain accessibility for mobility-impaired users; antifragile improvements cannot come at the cost of vulnerable group exclusion.
- **Participatory governance:** Task 2.2 stakeholder workshops must include representatives from vulnerable communities (elderly associations, disability advocacy groups, low-income neighborhood councils) to ensure their mobility needs inform parameter calibration and validation thresholds.
- **Transparent communication:** All adaptations (especially pricing, service reductions) must be communicated through multiple channels (physical notices, community meetings, simple language) accessible to non-digital populations, not solely through apps or websites.
- **Monitoring exclusion effects:** Track disaggregated metrics: ridership changes by income quintile, accessibility changes by disability status, app compliance rates by age group. If any subgroup shows systematic degradation, trigger human review via the exploratory decision tier (Section 6.8).

The framework’s equity indicator $Q(t)$ captures distributional outcomes, but ethical implementation demands proactive inclusion of vulnerable voices in decision-making, not merely post-hoc measurement of inequality. Antifragility that benefits only the digitally-connected or economically-privileged contradicts the framework’s foundational commitment to equitable urban mobility.

12.1.3 Institutional Coordination

Successful implementation depends on strong coordination among transport authorities, operators, and municipal agencies, aligned through formal agreements and review mechanisms.

Table 9: Required Institutional Partnerships

Partner Type	Role in Framework	Coordination Mechanism
Transport authority	Policy approval, budget	Guided/exploratory tiers
Traffic management	Real-time data, signal control	Automated tier
Transit operators	AFC data, service changes	Data sharing agreement
Energy utilities	SCADA access	Optional MoU
Telecom providers	CDR, ICT uptime	Privacy-preserving API
Municipal planning	Equity data, constraints	Quarterly review

12.2 Implementation Roadmap

In this section, a phased path from theory to operation is outlined.

12.2.1 Phase 1: Theoretical Completion (Current - D2.3)

This phase defines the theoretical architecture, validation logic, and documentation that form the basis for all subsequent implementation activities.

- Define all model components
- Specify validation protocols
- Document dependencies
- Create city templates

12.2.2 Phase 2: Calibration and Pilot Testing

In this phase, parameters will be calibrated using real data from initial pilot sites through Task 2.2 workshops and benchmark experiments.

- Task 2.2 workshops for parameter elicitation
- Data access negotiations
- Benchmark network back-testing
- Initial city calibration (one pilot)
- Sensitivity analysis with city data

12.2.3 Phase 3: Multi-City Validation

The framework will then be validated across all pilot cities to test cross-city generalization and long-term anti-fragility performance.

- Deploy in all three pilot cities
- Cross-city external validation
- Refinement based on operational feedback
- Long-term (6-month) AF tracking

12.2.4 Phase 4: Operational Integration

Finally, validated models will be integrated into institutional workflows, establishing automated, guided, and exploratory tiers for continuous anti-fragility management.

- Real-time implementation with automated tier
- Integration with existing traffic management systems
- Continuous learning and parameter updates
- Dissemination and replication framework

12.3 Risk Mitigation Strategies

We match likely risks to practical safeguards.

Table 10: Implementation Risks and Mitigations

Risk	Impact	Mitigation
Data sparsity (<30%)	Degrades accuracy	Tiered implementation, proxies
Policy inertia	Delayed P(t) changes	Document timelines, use lags
Institutional resistance	Blocks automated tier	Start with exploratory only
External validity concerns	Limited transferability	Multi-city validation
Black swan events	Model breakdown	Explicit scope limits
Computational limits	Slow convergence	Optimize Layer 1 solver
Equity violations	Social backlash	Hard constraint in \mathcal{C}

13 Theoretical Contributions and Novelty

This section highlights how the antifragile equilibrium framework advances the theoretical understanding of urban mobility systems beyond resilience toward adaptive improvement.

13.1 Advances Beyond State of the Art

We identify the key conceptual and methodological innovations that distinguish this deliverable from existing equilibrium and resilience models in transport systems.

1. **Dual-model architecture:** First framework to explicitly separate strategic Target-Setting Model from operational equilibrium finding (3-layer), enabling clearer validation and modular implementation.
2. **Formal antifragility quantification:** AF with statistical thresholds (AF_{req} , AF_{crit}) that are context-adaptive rather than fixed, addressing the theoretical gap between resilience (return to baseline) and antifragility (exceed baseline).
3. **Causal learning integration:** First equilibrium model to embed causal inference (SCM + ablation) directly into the capacity update mechanism via L_{trace} , ensuring structural changes are evidence-based.
4. **Dynamic information entropy normalization:** Topology-aware information entropy measure $H_{norm} = C/C_{max}(\text{current_topology})$ that adjusts to network changes, solving the measurement problem during disruptions.
5. **Homeostasis framework for transport:** Application of biological homeostasis principles (governing variables, receptors, control centers, effectors) to urban mobility, providing a conceptual bridge between system dynamics and transport planning.
6. **Multi-timescale learning:** Two-timescale update (η_s, η_ℓ) with Antifragility Gate creating a principled mechanism for temporary vs. permanent adaptations, addressing the exploration-exploitation trade-off in system learning.
7. **Equity-constrained antifragility:** Hard constraint $Q(t+1) - Q(t) \leq 0$ and monotone neural network architecture ensure improvements do not come at the cost of increased inequality, advancing normative transport theory.
8. **PESTLE-aware validation:** Explicit mapping of political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental constraints into mathematical feasibility sets and decision tiers.

13.2 Theoretical Limitations and Scope

We also delineate the assumptions and boundaries of the proposed theory to clarify its intended domain of validity and avoid overextension beyond current data or governance constraints.

- **Supply-side simplification:** Model does not include explicit operator profit maximization or competitive equilibrium. Appropriate for publicly-operated European systems; would require extension for privatized contexts.
- **Behavioral homogeneity:** Logit model assumes representative agents; does not capture full heterogeneity in preferences, information access, or decision-making processes.
- **Perfect foresight in UE:** Wardrop equilibrium assumes travelers have perfect knowledge of costs; does not model learning dynamics or bounded rationality.
- **Linear target function:** $\bar{E}(x)$ is linear in indicators; may miss important nonlinear interactions (though nonlinearity enters through D_{eff} , $\psi(C)$, and link costs).

-
- **Stationary environments:** Model assumes parameter stability between disruptions; long-term trends (climate change, demographic shifts) require recalibration.
 - **Extreme events:** Not designed for cascading failures or "black swan" events beyond historical experience; validation limited to moderate-to-severe disruptions.
 - **Spatial aggregation:** Grid-based representation may miss micro-scale equity issues or localized disruptions.

14 Conclusions

This section synthesizes the theoretical findings, confirming how the proposed framework advances antifragile urban mobility and outlining directions for application in future phases.

14.1 Summary of Theoretical Framework

This deliverable has specified a comprehensive theoretical framework for antifragile urban mobility equilibrium. The framework consists of two integrated models:

1. **The Target-Setting Model** establishes what performance level the system should achieve post-disruption through:
 - Formal state representation $G = (S, u)$ with normalized KPIs
 - Target performance function $\bar{E}(x) = \lambda \bar{E}^+ - (1 - \lambda) \bar{E}^-$
 - Convergence dynamics via $\dot{E} = -\kappa(E - \bar{E})$
 - Statistical AF validation with context-adaptive thresholds
 - Disturbance integration from D2.1 event catalogue
2. **The Three-Layer Equilibrium Model** operationalizes how the system reaches those targets through:
 - Layer 1: Wardrop traffic flow equilibrium
 - Layer 2: Discrete choice modal split equilibrium
 - Layer 3: System Responsiveness Index with causal learning
 - Antifragility Gate for validation before permanent changes
 - Two-timescale updates (η_s, η_ℓ) for temporary vs. structural adaptations

The integration of these models creates a learning loop where validated shock improvements permanently raise system baseline performance and resilience.

14.2 Addressing the Research Questions

We revisit each research question to show how the theoretical framework and derived models collectively provide clear and complete answers.

RQ1: State representation $G = (S, u)$. We define S as the governing-variable vector encompassing network topology, capacities, flows, and modal shares, with mapping $u(S) = V$ to 12 normalized KPIs measuring throughput, redundancy, adaptation, information entropy, disturbance, stress, equity, pricing, behavior, energy, ICT, and synergy. The 30-day rolling normalization ensures dynamic bounding while maintaining comparability.

RQ2: Receptor-control-effector loops. Receptors = data collection (sensors, surveys, logs); Control centers = Target-Setting Model + Equilibrium model Layer 3 (SRI, causal learning); Effectors = capacity updates via c_{t+1} projection, modal service changes, pricing policies. PESTLE constraints formalized through feasible set \mathcal{C} and three-tier decision system.

RQ3: Antifragility Factor formalization. $AF = \mu_{30} / E_{\text{base}}$ with two thresholds: requirement-based $AF_{\text{req}} = 1 + 0.2(1 - E_{\text{base}})$ accounting for diminishing returns, and statistical $AF_{\text{crit}} = 1 + k\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$ controlling false positives. Decision via $\text{LCL}_{0.95}(AF) \geq \max\{AF_{\text{req}}, AF_{\text{crit}}\}$. City-neutral through local variance estimation.

RQ4: Layer coupling principles. Hierarchical solution with traffic flow (Layer 1) → modal split (Layer 2) → performance evaluation → SRI computation (Layer 3) → capacity update → iterate. Convergence ensured through: (i) strictly convex link costs; (ii) compact feasible set; (iii) bounded demands; (iv) step size conditions $\eta_s < 2/\lambda_{\max}(\nabla^2 E)$; (v) cross-layer consistency < 0.05 . Stability via a 5-period convergence test plus the no-drift condition.

RQ5: Validation criteria. Specified now for later testing: (i) Statistical—bootstrap CI, stability test, CUSUM control; (ii) Internal—SCM/ablation precision/recall $\geq 80\%$; (iii) External—leave-one-out cross-validation; (iv) Operational—equity non-worsening, cross-layer consistency, equilibrium verification. Back-testing protocol defined for benchmark networks and synthetic data before pilot deployment.

RQ6: City templating. Framework remains neutral through: (i) tiered data requirements (full/partial/minimal); (ii) city-specific parameter calibration via AHP + elastic-net; (iii) adaptive thresholds based on local variance; (iv) PESTLE mapping to local constraints; (v) Task 2.2 workshop integration for stakeholder preferences. Templates provided for Bratislava, Odessa, Larissa, and AHEPA Demo Site in Thessaloniki show adaptability while preserving theoretical structure.

14.3 Next Steps for Implementation

The following steps translate the theoretical work of D2.3 into concrete actions scheduled for upcoming work packages and pilot phases.

1. **Task 2.2 Workshops:** Parameter elicitation, constraint specification, data availability assessment in each pilot city.
2. **Data Access Agreements:** Negotiate MoUs with transport authorities, operators, utilities for critical data streams.
3. **Ethics Approval:** Complete DPIA, establish anonymization protocols, obtain consent frameworks.
4. **Benchmark Testing:** Validate model behavior on Sioux Falls and other canonical networks with known properties.
5. **Calibration:** Estimate city-specific parameters using 2019-2025 historical events and operational data.
6. **Pilot Deployment:** Phased rollout starting with exploratory tier, advancing to guided and automated as confidence builds.
7. **Long-term Validation:** 6-month AF tracking post-implementation to confirm sustained improvements.
8. **Refinement:** Continuous learning updates to weights, thresholds, and validation criteria based on operational experience.

14.4 Contribution to Project Objectives

This deliverable advances the project’s overall goal of engineering antifragile urban mobility systems by:

- Providing a rigorous mathematical foundation for “better-after-shock” systems
- Bridging theoretical transport equilibrium with resilience engineering
- Creating operational protocols that respect real-world constraints (PESTLE)
- Enabling evidence-based learning from disruptions through causal inference
- Ensuring equity remains a core requirement, not an afterthought
- Specifying validation criteria that prevent false claims of antifragility
- Offering adaptable templates for diverse city contexts

The framework is ready for operationalization in subsequent work packages, conditional on data partnerships and institutional readiness. All theoretical components are fully specified, falsifiable, and designed for empirical validation.

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Appendix

A Glossary of Terms

Antifragility Factor (AF): Ratio of post-disruption performance to baseline, $AF = \mu_{30} / E_{\text{base}}$. System is antifragile if $AF > \text{threshold}$.

Antifragility Gate: Validation mechanism requiring statistical, internal, and external criteria before temporary adaptations become permanent.

Performance Steady State: State where $dE/dt \approx 0$, indicating performance has stabilized (distinct from game-theoretic equilibria).

Dynamic Information Entropy: Network flow distribution measure $C(t)$ normalized by topology-dependent maximum $C_{\text{max}}(\text{topology}_t)$.

Feasible Set \mathcal{C} : Space of allowable network capacities respecting budget, geometry, safety, and equity constraints.

Governing Variables: The KPI vector $V = u(S)$ that characterizes system state, analogous to vital signs in biological homeostasis.

Homeostasis: Biological principle of maintaining internal stability through feedback; adapted here for urban mobility systems.

Modal Split Equilibrium: Distribution of trips across modes where no traveler can improve utility by switching modes unilaterally.

PESTLE: Framework for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental constraints.

Receptor-Control-Effector: Homeostatic loop: sensors (receptors) \rightarrow learning algorithms (control) \rightarrow policy changes (effectors).

System Responsiveness Index (SRI): Weighted combination of operational elasticity, infrastructure pressure, and causal learning index guiding capacity adjustments.

Two-Timescale Learning: Separation of fast temporary adaptations (η_s) from slow structural changes (η_ℓ) with 10:1 ratio.

Wardrop User Equilibrium: Traffic flow where all used routes between any OD pair have equal minimum travel time; no driver can unilaterally reduce their travel time.

B Complete Symbol Reference

Symbol	Definition	Unit/Range
$G = (S, u)$	State representation: governing variables and mapping	-
$S \in \mathbb{R}^n$	Governing variable vector	context-dependent
$u : S \rightarrow V$	Mapping from state to KPIs	-
$V \in [0, 1]^m$	Normalized KPI vector	dimensionless
$E(t) \in [0, 1]$	System performance score	dimensionless
$\bar{E}(x) \in [0, 1]$	Target performance	dimensionless
$M(t) \in [0, 1]$	Mobility throughput	trips/(h·cap)
$R(t) \in [0, 1]$	Redundancy ratio	dimensionless
$A(t) \in [0, 1]$	Adaptation velocity	%/day
$C(t) \in [0, 1]$	Network information entropy (normalized)	nats
$D_{\text{eff}}(t) \in [0, 1]$	Effective disturbance	dimensionless
$S(t) \in [0, 1]$	Stress index	dimensionless
$Q(t) \in [0, 1]$	Equity penalty (Theil-T)	dimensionless
$P(t) \in [0, 1]$	Demand management index	dimensionless
$B(t) \in [0, 1]$	Behavioral compliance	dimensionless
$E_{\text{energy}}(t) \in [0, 1]$	Energy resilience	dimensionless
$E_{\text{ICT}}(t) \in [0, 1]$	ICT uptime	dimensionless
$I(t) \in [0, 1]$	Intermodal synergy	dimensionless
$\mathbf{c}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{ A }$	Network capacity vector	veh/h
$\mathbf{f}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{ A }$	Link flow vector	veh/h
$\mathbf{m}_t \in [0, 1]^{ M }$	Modal split vector	proportion
$\alpha_i, i = 1, \dots, 4$	Positive component weights	sum to 1
$\beta_i, i = 1, 2$	Negative component weights	sum to 1
$\omega_i, i = 1, 2$	Infrastructure weights	sum to 1
ζ, θ, π, μ	Individual indicator weights	0.1–0.15
$\lambda = 0.7$	Performance balance weight	dimensionless
$\kappa = 0.1$	Convergence rate	per period
$\eta_s = 0.1$	Short-term learning rate	per iteration
$\eta_\ell = 0.01$	Long-term learning rate	per iteration
$\tau = 6$	Disturbance recency decay	days
$\tau_L = 30$	Memory decay constant	days
AF	Antifragility Factor	ratio
AF_{req}	Requirement threshold	> 1
AF_{crit}	Statistical threshold	> 1
$\text{SRI}(t)$	System Responsiveness Index	[0,1]
ε_{ops}	Operational elasticity	[0,1]
ρ_{infra}	Infrastructure pressure	[0,1]
L_{index}	Causal learning index	[-1,1]
L_{trace}	Causal trace component	[-1,1]
L_{pattern}	Pattern learning component	[0,1]
\mathcal{C}	Feasible capacity set	$\mathbb{R}^{ A }$
$\Pi_{\mathcal{C}}$	Projection onto feasible set	operator
\odot	Element-wise multiplication	operator
$\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$	Indicator function	{0,1}
$\theta = 0.1$	Logit scale parameter	dimensionless
H_{norm}	Normalized entropy	[0,1]
C_{max}	Maximum information entropy for topology	nats
N_{OD}	Number of OD pairs	count
$\hat{\sigma}_{\text{resid}}$	Residual standard deviation	dimensionless
k	Confidence multiplier	1.64 or 2.58
μ_{30}	30-day post-event mean	dimensionless
E_{base}	Pre-event baseline	dimensionless

C Parameter Summary Table

Parameter	Default	Meaning	Calibration
$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$	0.25 each	Weights on M, R, A, H_{norm}	AHP + elastic-net
β_1, β_2	0.57, 0.43	Weights on D_{eff} , S	AHP + elastic-net
ω_1, ω_2	0.5 each	Weights on energy, ICT	AHP + elastic-net
ζ	0.1	Weight on synergy I	Expert elicitation
θ	0.1	Weight on equity penalty Q	Expert elicitation
π	0.1	Weight on pricing P	Expert elicitation
μ	0.15	Weight on behavior B	Expert elicitation
λ	0.7	Positive/negative balance	Regression
κ	0.1	Convergence speed	Historical recovery
η_s	0.1	Short-term learning	Gradient stability
η_ℓ	0.01	Long-term learning	Ratio 10:1 to η_s
τ	6 days	Event recency decay	Cross-validation
τ_L	30 days	Memory decay	Empirical
k	1.64	Confidence multiplier	95% (default)
θ_{logit}	0.1	Modal choice scale	Literature
$\delta_{transport}$	1.0	Transport domain weight	D2.1 prevalence
$\delta_{weather}$	0.9	Weather domain weight	D2.1 prevalence
$\delta_{utilities}$	0.9	Utilities domain weight	D2.1 prevalence
δ_{social}	0.9	Social domain weight	D2.1 prevalence
$\omega_{src,official}$	1.0	Official source reliability	Expert judgment
$\omega_{src,operator}$	0.9	Operator source reliability	Expert judgment
$\omega_{src,sensor}$	0.9	Sensor source reliability	Expert judgment
$\omega_{src,social}$	0.6	Social source reliability	Expert judgment
$\omega_{src,survey}$	0.6	Survey source reliability	Expert judgment

D City-Specific Templating

These templates are illustrative examples pending Task 2.2 workshop outcomes and data availability assessments. Actual pilot configurations will be determined in Phase 2.

D.1 Bratislava Template

Expected characteristics:

- High data availability (smart card penetration >80%)
- Moderate network redundancy (radial + grid structure)
- Strong institutional coordination (single transport authority)
- Focus on equity between old town and suburbs

Model adaptations:

- Emphasize $Q(t)$ weight ($\theta = 0.15$ vs. default 0.10)
- Tighter equity constraint: $Q(t+1) - Q(t) \leq -0.01$ (improvement required)
- Higher confidence for AF validation: $k = 2.58$ (99%)
- Full data tier expected (>70% coverage)

D.2 Odessa Template

Expected characteristics:

- Medium data availability (reconstruction challenges)
- Low initial redundancy (post-conflict recovery)
- Emphasis on resilience and rapid adaptation
- Infrastructure pressure from displacement patterns

Model adaptations:

- Emphasize $R(t)$ weight ($\alpha_2 = 0.35$ vs. default 0.25)
- Lower $\kappa = 0.15$ (faster adaptation required)
- Relax data requirements to partial tier (30-70%)
- Higher weight on operational elasticity: $w_1 = 0.5$ in SRI
- Accept $AF_{req} = 1.05$ (lower threshold given context)

D.3 Larissa Template

Expected characteristics:

- Medium data availability (growing smart city initiatives)
- Seasonal demand variation (tourism, agricultural cycles)
- Environmental focus (sustainability goals)
- Limited multimodal integration currently

Model adaptations:

- Emphasize $I(t)$ weight ($\zeta = 0.15$ vs. default 0.10)
- Strong seasonal adjustment in baseline calculation
- Add environmental KPI to \bar{E}^+ (CO2 emissions)
- Medium data tier (50-70%) with proxy indicators
- Focus L_{pattern} on seasonal disruption patterns

D.4 AHEPA University Hospital DemoSite (Thessaloniki) Template

Expected characteristics:

- Hospital-centered mobility focus (emergency access, patient transport, staff commuting)
- High-density urban area with medical district constraints
- Critical infrastructure requiring high reliability (emergency vehicle routing)
- Mix of private vehicles, public transport, and medical shuttles
- Strong emphasis on accessibility for mobility-impaired populations

Model adaptations:

- Emphasize $S(t)$ stress minimization ($\beta_2 = 0.50$ vs. default 0.43) for emergency access reliability
- Critical link identification: flag hospital access routes as non-reducible capacity in \mathcal{C} constraints
- Enhanced equity focus: $Q(t)$ must explicitly account for disability access ($\theta = 0.15$)
- Higher confidence for antifragility validation in emergency corridors: $k = 2.58$ (99%)
- Specialized $I(t)$ synergy: include medical shuttle integration with public transport and private ambulance services
- Shorter adaptation timescale: $\kappa = 0.15$ for faster response to disruptions affecting hospital access
- Medium-to-high data tier expected (50–80%): hospital transport data available, but broader city coverage may be partial
- Add health-specific KPI to \bar{E}^+ : emergency vehicle response time or hospital accessibility index

Specific validation considerations:

- Antifragility assessed primarily on emergency access reliability, not system-wide throughput
- Layer 2 modal split includes medical transport modes (ambulances, patient shuttles, accessible taxis)
- Equity constraint must ensure improvements don't degrade access for mobility-impaired hospital visitors/patients
- Back-testing should use medical emergency scenarios (e.g., road closures during peak hours) rather than generic disruptions